

Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action

#8.6

Final Report on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

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List of Abbreviations

CSO	Civil society organisation
CSS	Citizen Social Science
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association

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EU	European Union
FARN	Fundación Ambiente y Recursos Naturales
FHP	Fachhochschule Potsdam
FSMC	Federació Salut Mental Catalunya
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OKF	Open Knowledge Foundation
R&I	Research and Innovation
UB	Universitat de Barcelona
UNIVIE	Universität Wien
UNSAM	Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
WP	Work Package
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (Centre for Social Innovation)

1 Executive Summary

This document is the final report for CoAct's consortium Communication and Dissemination (WP8) activities led by the Global Innovation Gathering e.V. (GIG).

The Deliverable D8.1 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan guided communication and dissemination activities, including objectives, target groups, outreach and engagement tools, channels, and tactics.

During the last 36 months, CoAct delivered the Citizen Social Science concepts and practices to more than 1,6 million people, using a wide range of communication strategies and tools, combined with intense resilience and creativity during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Furthermore, a strategy focused on constant feedback between global and local using digital communication tools contributed to the disseminated ideas and actions reaching a far wider audience than the ones around consortium partners.

This document includes partners' communication and dissemination activities and analyses CoAct actions, channels, and tools to convey the project and disseminate its results. It also presents WP8 overall progress based on the key performance indicators related to communication and dissemination.

2 Introduction

CoAct (Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action) proposes a radically new approach to facing global social issues by engaging vulnerable citizens as co-researchers. The strategy represents a reinvigorated understanding of Citizen Social Science, understood here as participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. CoAct's research approach, where citizen groups and their problems are at the core of the research questions, requires translating those attributes for its communicative and dissemination activities. CoAct's shared values – Inclusiveness, Horizontality, Equity, Trust and Respect, Open Science, Co-ownership, Empowerment, and Reflexivity – underlined the direction and structure of CoAct's communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (D8.1). This document (D8.6) describes and evaluates the communication and dissemination actions and provides reflections and recommendations for future projects. As previously emphasised, CoAct's communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (D8.1) and the interim report (D8.3) were the reference points for this evaluation.

2.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The objectives of CoAct's communication and dissemination strategy were to support all coalition partners to use communicational tactics and tools that allowed them to achieve the following goals:

- To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle;
- To increase scientific literacy, skills, competence, and public awareness regarding science;
- To disseminate CoAct and build a sustainable citizen social science community of practice.

The communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (D8.1) built on the ethical framework underlying CoAct by establishing guiding principles for all communication and dissemination-related decisions, thus addressing all WPs. The project was designed modularly, providing guiding steps to develop context-driven tactics managing the communication and dissemination activities underlying the eight WPs of CoAct.

The plan consisted of the following elements:

1. A strategic normative framework for decision-making
2. Strategy Design Guidelines supporting all consortium partners to align decisions and objectives on their communication and dissemination practices and materials
3. Visual Identity for all communication and dissemination materials
4. Results dissemination plan (Media planning templates)

Different milestones guided CoAct’s communication and dissemination activities. The context-driven guidance structure of the planning plan provided the crucial flexibility to evolve specific dissemination tools, and their content as necessity emerged throughout the process, overall and within the eight WPs.

Figure 1. Communication and Dissemination Timeline

The first year of CoAct (2020) focused on developing the project's communication and dissemination strategy alongside its corporate identity and design elements. A guideline manual was prepared with basic templates for presentations, reports, and social media posts on Twitter, Instagram and Facebook, enabling all partners to design their communication and dissemination materials.

On the overarching project level, communication and dissemination activities focused on raising awareness about the project and its methodology and actively engaging potentially relevant external actors to grow an international CSS community beyond the R&I Actions performed by CoAct. On the R&I action level, activities ranged from local outreach and engagement exercises to assembling Knowledge Coalitions, engaging relevant stakeholders, and creating awareness about the R&I Actions and respective developments. D8.3 further elaborates on this process.

The second year focused on additional engagement alongside the publication and spreading of first outcomes, lessons learned, and the concentration of different actors in conversations about the various project's thematic areas. Those activities' outreach and engagement multiplied through CoAct's and consortium partners' websites and social media channels. For example, the first outcomes of scoping studies and R&I Action outcomes were blog posts reflecting and sharing perspectives on CSS, inviting and engaging external communities of practice. To a large extent, these were likewise the outcomes of online events CoAct organised, combining formal webinars, immersing invited speakers, or informal hangouts, providing an open space for conversation on project-relevant topics.

These events aimed to disclose the shaping of the Citizen Social Science approach from diverse perspectives and geographies. These activities partially belonged to the project's dedicated community-building workstream, seeking to co-create discourse and formats deriving from the articulated needs of interested civil society actors. As a starting point, an open community call set an agenda and created a CSS messenger chat group. These co-

created and iterative processes could organise frequent thematically focused gatherings. Lessons learned from the external feedback alongside co-evaluation informed the adaptation of methodological steps. These learning processes are documented in written and audio-visual materials and disseminated via various communication channels.

The third year continued to communicate and discuss CoAct activities and learnings via internal and external events. Exposure was through publicity via the website and interior and institutional social media channels, whilst blog posts summarised and disseminated internally hosted webinars, hangouts and other activities. Findings from the R&I Actions and the co-evaluation processes are in policy briefs, whitepapers, academic articles, and the final report. Experienced methods are available in a toolkit accessible on the project website, including additional data and details. A significant contribution to achieving a diversified reflection on CSS has been co-creating a Global Perspectives publication, bringing civil society actors from around the world and sharing their thoughts and local community practices. A final event week brought together community members, partners, co-researchers, and the general public to reflect upon the outcomes in two dedicated panel discussions. An online video premiere showcasing CoAct's work of the last three years celebrated results furthermore.

3 Communication and dissemination tools

3.1 Website

CoAct's central communication and dissemination environment is its multilanguage website (English, Spanish, German, and Catalan), www.coactproject.eu. All information about the

project, including all materials and news updates, are centrally shared on the website, from where they are further distributed throughout the project's social media channels and the consortium member's institutional channels.

A project website is a crucial communication tool to inform its activities, news and events while disseminating the gathered knowledge and its results to a wide range of target groups, including civil society organisations, worldwide researchers, international networks and associations, and EU policymakers.

Figure 2. Welcome Page CoAct website

All the content on the website is under an Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>). This licence lets others remix, tweak, and build upon the work, including for commercial purposes, as long as they credit it and licence their new creations under identical terms. Consortium partners co-created and further

co-developed the website structure over the years, acting upon new outputs and emerging needs. The current website structure is as follows:

3.1.1 Landing page

The landing page is the central news hub of the project. It presents a brief about CoAct with a learn more button, blog posts with the latest news related to the project, an overview of the consortium partners involved, and links to CoAct's social media channels, besides legal terms and content.

3.1.2 About page: What is CoAct, our ethical values, partners and advisory board

1. The "What is CoAct" section explains how the consortium understands social science and through which core activities the project seeks to enact such understanding, such as thematic and local integration, citizens as equal stakeholders, and bottom-up collaboration for robust social knowledge production. The site also entails a short video introducing CoAct and its approach.
2. The "ethical values" section introduces the coalition-wide created and embraced values underlying the project and its activities, namely inclusiveness, horizontality, equity, trust and respect, open science, co-ownership, empowerment, and reflexivity.
3. The "partner" section introduces the consortium members. It outlines the respective expertise each partner brings to the project, including the responsibilities each member holds throughout the project, deriving from their disciplinary focus, such as Participatory Action Research, Computational Social Science, Citizen Science, Research Policy and Development,

Digital Transformation, Social Movement Studies and Participatory Development Communication.

4. The advisory board section presents the international group of experts responsible for overseeing the project's activities and outputs and providing timely and relevant feedback on processes and results.

3.1.3 R&I Actions page

Each R&I Action has its section page (Mental Health Care in Barcelona, Youth Employment in Vienna, Environmental Justice in Buenos Aires and Gender Equality in Europe as research pilots on which the respective R&I Action introduces the relevance of CSS in the separate thematic area, how it will be implemented, and a timeline showcasing the activities undertaken within the R&I action over time.

Figure 3. Activity Timeline R&I Action Mental Health Care in Barcelona

3.1.4 Resources page: Publications, Videos, Policy briefs and whitepapers, Global Perspectives, CSS School Open Materials, Project reports, Readings, Zenodo Community

The resources section provides a comprehensive, easy-to-search overview of all outputs generated throughout the project period.

1) Publications

It is a selection of 12 CoAct project scientific publications. They are all open access, hosted in scientific publishers' platforms committed to open science.

2) Videos

A collection of all videos published by CoAct Consortium Partners. Themes and R&I Actions categorise them. There are 36 videos published in December 2022

3) Policy briefs and whitepapers

A page to share the four policy briefs and two whitepapers produced by CoAct project after three years.

4) Global Perspectives

This page is a CoAct online co-publication that brings together voices from around the globe to unpack what Citizen Social Science needs to account for to be truly inclusive. In a series of blog posts, voices from diverse contexts share what science should look like when accounting for multiple voices, needs, and traditions worldwide.

5) CSS School Open Materials

A space is presenting the results from the Citizen Social Science School. Its main goal was to offer academic researchers a commonplace and shared time to reflect, discuss, learn, and receive practical guidelines to explore social

dimensions behind a broad set of Citizen Science practices related to social issues and when involving groups and persons in a vulnerable situation acting as co-researchers. The page brings information about the course and its participants, the learning outcomes and all the school reference material. Furthermore, it presents seven workshop videos and links to all panellists' presentations.

6) Project Reports

This page conveys public WP deliverables. It presents 18 deliverables from different WPs.

7) Readings

CoAct's academic resources are organised by tags and categories (e.g., citizen science, inclusive research, open science, participatory action research). One thousand fifty articles and scientific resources are available, all connected to the CSS landscape. The texts are indexed in Zotero, a free and open-source reference management software to manage bibliographic data and related research materials, such as PDF files (<https://www.zotero.org/>).

8) Figure 4. Zotero reading on CoAct’s website

9) Zenodo Community

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN (<https://zenodo.org/>). It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and other research-related digital artefacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citeable. The platform also helps keep track of documents' views and downloads. In December 2022, CoAct's Zenodo has 59 publications.

3.1.5 Toolkit page

The Toolkit section is an open resource introducing the CoAct research cycle. For each research step, the Toolkit makes methods available that the coalition partners use in their work. The toolkit also provides valuable resources, for instance, elaborating on how specific

procedures have been used in practice and videos with CSS experts. It allows for the easy adoption of the CSS approach by civil society organisations, NGOs, public bodies, and social innovators. The Toolkit provides academic and non-academic researchers, community partners, and citizen initiatives with tools and methods to develop their CSS projects in local settings. It provides a framework to practice community-based research and collective action for citizens. One can find more information about the Toolkit in the Deliverable 2.4

Figure 5. Toolkit Main Page

3.1.6 Blog and events page

This section lists all the events and the latest news about the project. While the events section announced hangouts, webinars and conferences organised or attended by CoAct members, the blog was a living record of information, reflections and actions on Citizen Social Science.

Figure 6. Event Section

Blog entries written by different partners share their lessons learned and experiences from activities they have participated in or activities within their R&I Actions.

Figure 7. Blog section

In total, there are 59 publications among blog entries and events shared, as listed below:

Table 1. Blog posts and events entries

Date	Title	Categories
22-05-2020	CoAct Proposal	News
22-05-2020	D8.1 CoAct Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan	News
23-06-2020	Citizen Social Science in times of COVID-19: CoActFrenaLaCurva Digital Hackathon	Blog
06-07-2020	Open Science Diplomacy to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic	Blog
08-09-2020	ECSA; Sept. 8th, 2020	Events
24-09-2020	Call for Videos Shaping Citizen Social Science together	Blog
24-09-2020	RICAP Sept. 24th, 2020	Events
14-10-2020	CS SDG Oct. 14-15th, 2020	Events
31-10-2020	UNDP- Oct. 29th, 2020	Events
02-12-2020	dots - the Impact Summit	Blog
07-12-2020	CoAct Consortium Meeting	Blog
10-12-2020	DOTS- Dec. 10-11th, 2020	Events
21-12-2020	CoAct Webinar- Jan. 27th, 2021	Events
01-02-2021	Wrapping up CoAct Riachuelo's 2020: Co-designing a Citizen Social Science project in the COVID-19 context in Argentina	Blog
12-02-2021	A new family is born: Join CoAct's *Open*Citizen*Social*Science community	Blog
31-03-2021	Community hangout- Apr. 20th, 2021	Events
19-04-2021	CoAct Webinar May. 5th, 2021	Events
07-05-2021	Announcement *Open*Citizen*Social*Science hangout CoAct, April 21, 2021	Blog
09-06-2021	Registrations for the CoAct CSS school (September 13-23, 2021) are open!	Blog
11-06-2021	CoAct Webinar -; June. 22nd, 2021	Events
01-07-2021	Applications for the CoAct Open Calls on Gender Equality (July 1st, 2021-September 30th, 2021) are open!	Blog
27-07-2021	CoAct Q&A Session - August. 5th, 2021	Events

07-09-2021	2nd CoAct Q&A Session – September 9th, 2021	Events
15-09-2021	Conference Track: Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Science & Sept. 27th-29th, 2021	Events
14-10-2021	Gender Equality hangout: Oct. 21st, 2021	Events
26-10-2021	Accounting for Gender Equality in *Open*Citizen*Social Science – Acknowledge and Embrace People’s Life Cycles	Blog
10-11-2021	November hangout & Nov. 18th, 2021	Events
01-12-2021	CoAct open calls on Gender Equality: Welcome to our winners	Blog
20-12-2021	We invite you to the Citizen Social Science “CoAct for Mental Health” chatbot!	Blog
09-03-2022	CoAct partner member Valeria Arza was awarded in Argentina for her work as an outstanding researcher.	Blog
06-04-2022	Our first 2022 hangout is around the corner!	Events
14-04-2022	Join our monthly discussion around Shaping and Inclusive Citizen Social Science!	Blog
25-04-2022	Locally driven protocols and local traditions in the Open Citizen Social Sciences	News
06-05-2022	Forum on impact assessment in citizen science	Events
09-05-2022	CALL FOR CONTRIBUTIONS: Shaping an inclusive *Open *Citizen *Social Science landscape– Voices and methods from around the world	Blog
10-05-2022	Time for our second 2022 hangout: The Ownership of Science	Events
15-06-2022	Join our 3rd CoAct hangout 2022: Decolonizing our educational/institutional influences	Events
20-06-2022	Diversifying the ownership of science: lessons from our 3rd community hangout	News
27-06-2022	Decentralising Science – Locally driven validation protocols in Mboalab Cameroon	News
05-07-2022	Join the public consultation on the 6 Principles of co-evaluation	News
07-07-2022	Water quality and citizen social science in Buenos Aires	Blog
27-07-2022	Decolonising our educational/institutional influence: Towards open science funding and mental decolonisation	News

02-08-2022	Join our 4th CoAct hangout 2022 -; Practices to overcome false representation in participatory processes.	Events
22-08-2022	Outcomes from our Open Call on Gender Equality	News
22-08-2022	Learn more about CoAct and its Citizen Social Science actions	Blog
30-08-2022	Grantee Workshop Documentation	Blog
05-09-2022	NEW DATE: CoAct hangout on practices to overcome false representation in participatory processes	News
06-09-2022	Examples of and learnings from ethical standard setting in OCSS communities	News
20-09-2022	Register now! Ethical Standard Setting in OCSS communities	Events
26-09-2022	How to Navigate CoAc's Zotero Library	Blog
03-10-2022	Participatory Evaluation for sustainable social transformation: the CoAct Co-Evaluation Whitepaper	News
04-10-2022	Final Event Week	News
10-10-2022	Overcoming False Representation – Nurturing a shared understanding of concepts and opening up knowledge in cross-disciplinary research	News
02-11-2022	Ethical standard setting in OCSS communities	News
03-11-2022	Environmental Justice in Argentina: new poster launched!	Blog
11-11-2022	Open Citizen Social Science and Collaboration; A key element in driving STEM Education in South Sudan.	News
16-11-2022	Re-Invent learning. Or how making fosters empowerment and active participation	News
21-11-2022	Discourse on Decolonizing the Education System in South Sudan	News
05-12-2022	White Paper on Citizen Social Science applied to Civic Organisation Projects.	Policy briefs and whitepapers
05-12-2022	Citizen Social Science for Sanitation Policy in the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin	Policy briefs and whitepapers
05-12-2022	Policy Guidelines and Recommendations for New Social Measures on Youth Employment	Policy briefs and whitepapers
05-12-2022	Brief on policy recommendations to promote and strengthen mental health social support networks	Policy briefs and whitepapers
05-12-2022	Global Perspectives Launch Event	News

Final event week is a particular sub-page dedicated to promoting the last week's event dissemination campaign.

3.1.7 The Community page

The community page was set up together with CoAct's first activities to grow a diverse and geographically dispersed community of civil society actors seeking to critically discuss what is required to raise a genuinely inclusive CSS approach. Via the page, visitors can join the dedicated signal group. The page also hosts a section about the CSS summer school that took place in 2021 and was an effort to create a community of young academics. Lastly, the page hosts a section showcasing a series of videos that several members had made to showcase their understanding of CSS and its effect on their work.

3.1.8 The manual website page

The manual page provides seven videos on editing and publishing on CoAct's website. It also contains further links to WordPress publishing procedures. It is available (not to the general public) at <https://coactproject.eu/manual/>.

3.1.9 Website numbers

Access to the project website is monitored and reported upon using the [WP Statistics](#) and [Matomo](#) tools. Although both open-source tools provide impressive statistics while providing

sufficient privacy for the visitors, the use of two different analytics software is due to the possibility of improving personal analytical capabilities.

The Project Key Performance Indicator for the website sets at 200 visits/month with an average session of 2 minutes. A summary of the number of current users and average session of CoAct website follows.

From the website launch (March 2020) to December 13, 2021, CoAct website had 179,058 visits from 81,967 visitors. It means around 2.561,46 visitors per month, beyond the 500 visits proposed in the Grant Agreement. The rise in visits during hangouts, webinars and hangouts promotion campaigns is notable, especially **from December 2020** onwards.

Figure 8. Visits to CoAct website

Matomo average analyses show that visits had **a 1 min 58s** average duration, **two** actions per visit (like page views, PDF downloads, out links or internal site searches), and that **68%** of the visits have bounced, meaning visitors left the website after one page.

Figure 9. Matomo analysis overview details: average visits to CoAct website and visitors' behaviour

Further observations from the website statistics analysis are worthy of presenting. First, when not directly typing CoAct URL on the browser's address bar, most of the visits to the website come from Google (4.449), Twitter (1.106) and Facebook (229, in the sum of the desktop version and the mobile version). The following referring sites are CoAct Project hot site at the University of Vienna (173 visits); Baidu, the most famous Chinese search engine, with 158 visits; and the EU Citizen Science portal, with 122 visits, ahead of prominent social media or search engine platforms, like LinkedIn (122 visits) or Bing (89 visits).

Figure 10. Top Referring Sites

Rating	Site Url	Site Title	Server IP	Country	References
1	www.google.com	Google	172.217.18.4		4,449
2	t.co	t.co / Twitter	104.244.42.5		1,106
3	coactproject.univie.ac.at	CoAct - Citizen Social Science	131.130.70.24		173
4	baidu.com	---	220.181.38.148		158
5	eu-citizen.science	EU-Citizen.Science	51.178.141.110		128
6	www.linkedin.com	LinkedIn: Log In or Sign Up	13.107.42.14		122
7	m.facebook.com	Facebook #00 Anmelden oder Registrieren	185.60.217.35		120
8	bit.ly	Bitly URL Shortener Short URLs & Custom Free Link Shortener	67.199.248.10		113
9	i.facebook.com	Facebook - Anmelden oder Registrieren	185.60.217.37		109
10	www.bing.com	Bing	204.79.197.200		89
11	www.cs-sdg-conference.berlin	Host Europe GmbH - www.cs-sdg-conference.berlin	91.250.67.2		88
12	sg.shu.ct.net	Google Global Ranking	161.117.125.79		85
13	mail.google.com	---	142.250.186.133		80
14	www.zsi.at	ZSI - Zentrum für Soziale Innovation	193.170.154.233		74
15	ec.europa.eu	European Commission Choose your language Choisir une langue Wählen Sie eine Sprache	147.67.34.30		71
16	buff.ly	Simpler social media tools for authentic engagement Buffer	67.199.248.13		65
17	linktr.ee	Link in bio tool: Everything you are, in one simple link Linktree	151.101.2.133		54
18	www.fh-potsdam.de	Fachhochschule Potsdam	2.56.97.195		52
19	www.up2europe.eu	Up2Europe homepage - Ideas Accelerator for European Cooperation - Up2Europe	213.186.33.69		49
20	bildungswissenschaft.univie.ac.at	Institut für Bildungswissenschaft	131.130.70.24		48
21	www.google.de	Google	142.250.185.99		44
22	www.google.es	Google	142.250.74.195		38
23	duckduckgo.com	DuckDuckGo #00 Privacy, simplified.	40.114.177.156		37
24	www.google.ca	Google	216.58.212.163		32
25	www.google.com.hk	Google	142.250.185.67		28

Furthermore, the Gender Equality Open Call page (2657 visits), What is CoAct page (2576), and the CSS Summer School page (1.829) were the most visited ones, after the homepage, with 17,063 visits.

Figure 11. Most Visited Pages

ID	Title	Link	Visits
1	Home Page	/	17,063
2	Gender Equality	/opencalls/	2,657
3	What is CoAct?	/what-is-coact/	2,576
4	CSS Summer School	/citizen-social-science-school-social-dimensions-in-citizen-science/	1,829
5	CoAct Webinar Jan. 27th, 2021	/news/coact-webinar-co-shaping-evaluation-in-citizen-science/	1,755
6	Community video contributions	/overview/	1,619
7	Environmental Justice	/environmental-justice/	1,153
8	Partners	/partners/	1,115
9	Mental Health Care	/mental-health-care/	1,081
10	Get involved	/get-involved/	1,078

The top 15 countries where visitors come from are headed by the USA, with 22,152 visitors, followed by Germany (8,945), France (6,165), United Kingdom (3,850), and, in the fifth position, China with 2,967 visitors.

Figure 12. Top Visitors' Country

Rank	Flag	Country	Visitor Count
1		United States	22,152
2		Germany	8,945
3		France	6,165
4		United Kingdom	3,850
5		China	2,967
6		Spain	2,850
7		Singapore	2,725
8		Netherlands	2,663
9		Italy	2,548
10		India	2,114
11		Austria	1,783
12		Canada	1,756
13		Russian Federation	1,524
14		Viet Nam	1,498
15		Brazil	1,126

The website KPI for the 3rd year of the project is 500 visits a month with an average session of 2 minutes. Currently, the number of visitors to the platform is three times higher, with around 2500 visitors per month. But the average session is 2min and 58sec, meaning it is 2 seconds below the proposed parameter.

3.2 Social Media

Social media channels are vital for communication and dissemination as they facilitate two-way communication and further distribution of CoAct information and materials through other users. The CoAct project engaged a diverse audience of academic, policy, and civil society actors on its Twitter, Facebook (both @CoActeu) and Instagram (@coact.eu) pages. The social

media account's posts revolve around the associated areas of citizen social science, citizen science, open science, and other related topics. They also promote blog posts, events, hangouts, webinars, conferences, and R&I Actions activities. All consortium partners can contribute by sharing their news.

Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook provide tools for each channel metrics analysis. Currently, the number of followers on Twitter is 568, on Instagram is 131, and on Facebook, 77. All consortium partners play an essential role in the dissemination strategy: from sharing updates and news to collectively shaping the social media agenda to reposting CoAct social media posts via their institutional channels to multiply reach, diversify the audience, and potentially engage the community further. For example, UNIVIE's Instagram account (@coactvienna) in German is a channel with 205 followers to directly communicate with their target groups, young people, youth workers and Austrian organisations.

Through the joint engagement of all partners, redistributing CoAct's activities via their social media channels, we can count followers to CoAct's actions as presented below:

Table 2. CoAct's social media channels and followers

Social Media Channel	Followers
CoAct Social Media Channels	
Instagram	131
Facebook/Meta	77
Twitter	568
Partners' Social Media Channels	
University of Barcelona/Open Systems Twitter	2058

Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI) Twitter	1329
Zentrum für Soziale Innovation Reesearch Twitter	1576
University of Wien CoAct Twitter	36
University of Wien CoAct Instagram	203
Global Innovation Gathering Instagram	577
Global Innovation Gathering Facebook	2245
Global Innovation Gathering Twitter	2213
Linkedin GIG	1075
Total	12088

Social Media Channel	Total Followers
Total Instagram	911
Total Facebook	2322
Total Twitter	6451
Total Linkedin	1075

The expected number of followers per channel for M24 was 1.5K followers on Twitter, 1.5K on Facebook, and 300 on Instagram. Consortium partners constantly support sharing CoAct-related news, events, and project updates on their social media channels, plus the CoAct channels' activities made it possible to outnumber the expected followers. In addition to a qualitative approach, focusing on activities building a sustainable community of practice, like instant message groups, webinars, hangouts, co-authorship on blog posts, physical meetings, and YouTube playlists, CoAct's activities reached thousands of people. Moreover, Twitter impressions, just in CoAct channel alone, got more than 55,700 people since May 2020. It means that each Twitter receives an average of almost 1800 visualisations every month, as impressions include the times a Tweet appears in one of your followers' timelines and non-followers timelines.

CoAct's Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram timelines share more than 650 posts and reach more than 60,000 people. By adding numbers from all other partners' social media channels, CoAct posts outreach is more than 200,000 people.

3.3 Press Releases, newsletters and direct emails

Among communication tools, CoAct and its consortium partners used regular newsletters, press releases and direct e-mails to keep its members informed about its activities, news and events.

An e-mail newsletter is a powerful tool for staying connected with stakeholders. Newsletter tools used differ based on partners' preferable setups, the most common being MailChimp (<https://mailchimp.com>), SendingBlue (<https://pt.sendinblue.com>) and MailPoet (<https://www.mailpoet.com>).

Furthermore, press releases submitted to media channels could portray the project's activities in newsletters, blogs, magazines, radio and broadcasted TV programs.

All combined, those actions helped CoAct reach up to 650.000 people in its target groups. A comprehensive list of these actions is in [Annexe 1](#).

4 Events

CoAct has been organised and presented at European and international conferences, reaching an audience of approximately 20,000 people. (See Annexe 1 for the complete list of events and more details).

Highlights for presentations at the ECSA Conference in 2020 and 2021, sharing the latest ideas in the field with the citizen science community – citizen scientists and practitioners, researchers and policymakers; And for the active participation in 2 presentations and three workshops during the conference Knowledge for Change 2020. In 2021, a big shout to the involvement in the annual Citizen Social Science Association Conference.

In 2022, re:publica festival in Berlin was a landmark for the return of face-to-face events, and CoAct partners held a searing meetup discussion in June. Also, in 2022, a series of online hangouts lead to a joint online publication about global perspectives on citizen social science. Some of the activities carried out during the project are worthy of note, as follows:

4.1 CSS Summer School

From September 13–23, 2021, CoAct organised its Citizen Social Science School. The main goal was to offer academic researchers a common space and a shared time to reflect, discuss, learn, and receive practical guidelines to explore social dimensions behind a comprehensive set of Citizen Science practices related to social issues and when involving groups and persons in a vulnerable situation acting as co-researchers.

It was a rich program, including seminars with round tables, workshops, mentoring and working sessions. Those are the learning outcomes from the activity:

- Review of transdisciplinary aspects in the context of Citizen Social Science (e.g. Open Science, Ethical Research, Digital participation, Co-evaluation and Policy Impact)
- Practical examples of Citizen Social Science practices where groups in a vulnerable situation are acting as co-researchers
- Portfolio of collaborative, participatory research models (interdisciplinary, intersectoral and international)
- Practical tools to maximise success and minimise challenges of Citizen Social Science
- Development of an international network of peers
- Strategies to be inclusive in a citizen science project
- All the classes and content produced for the summer school can be accessed on the website: <https://coactproject.eu/open-materials-citizen-social-science-school/>

4.2 Webinars

In 2021, CoAct project adapted to the new COVID-19 regulations by organising a series of webinars, such as follows:

- On January 27th, 2021, the first public CoAct webinar took place: Co-shaping evaluation in Citizen Science? Towards more participatory approaches in evaluating Citizen Science in cooperation with ECSA and EU-Citizen.Science.
- On May 5th, 2021, the webinar theme was Digital Youth Work. Challenges, Tools and Impact, where experts in digital youth work shared how to include 'hard-to-reach' youth

in digital youth work, discuss best practice examples and address the question of impact evaluation.

Figure 13. Co-shaping evaluation in citizen science?

- In June. 22nd, 2021, CoAct’s third webinar discussed the framing of science by learning how scientific rigour research works outside academia. The first step to growing a global perspective which learning from participatory research initiatives in different contexts when asking questions.

4.3 Community Hangouts

In 2022, CoAct organised and hosted various online events, such as the Community Hangouts: A series of nine online community meetings that contributed to shaping a global bottom-up perspective on how science should/is be thought of and addressed, and how inclusive, bottom-up practices are enabled in the most diverse contexts worldwide. With participants from all continents, it highlighted best practices and lessons learned. Community Hangouts were a sharing knowledge space to support other actors shaping their respective communities while learning from their experiences.

Figure 14. Hangout Announcement

The meetings resulted in the co-creation process of a publication consisting of civil society contributions via blog posts addressing five core topics that the community had identified as crucial to address to develop a decolonial and genuinely inclusive approach to CSS. Between

April and November 2022, each hangout addressed a specific topic and invited people to contribute to the writing of a blog post. In December 2022, an online launch event for the resulting publication provided a platform for authors and readers to meet and discuss.

4.4 Jornadas CoActuem. Salud mental y justicia medioambiental

In May 2022, participants from the CoAct Justicia Ambiental team in Buenos Aires, Argentina, explained how they co-designed a digital platform promoting transformative actions in the Matanza-Riachuelo watershed. They presented their tool allowing meaningful participation of people directly affected by environmental pollution along the southern periphery of Buenos Aires, Argentina, where 5 million people live.

Learn more at

<https://comunitat.canodrom.barcelona/assemblies/comunitat/f/1651/meetings/2398?locale=es>

4.5 Consortium meeting in Barcelona

From May 30th till June 1st, CoAct hosted its annual consortium meeting in Barcelona. After two years of remote sessions due to the Covid pandemic, the three-day gathering marked a vital momentum for a direct encounter, engagement, and community strengthening. During that time, CoAct consortium partners set goals for the remaining project time, invested in 'hands-on' knowledge sharing about the R&I Actions and the Co-Evaluation process, and made final collective decisions about the toolkit, one of CoAct's core deliverables. Furthermore, partners co-designed Final Event Week objectives and the first program draft. Moreover, it was an opportunity to review the project's KPIs and to make crucial decisions about policy briefs and whitepapers.

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The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 873048

4.6 Final Conference Week

In October 2022, CoAct organised a final event week consisting of three days with diverse activities. The event aimed to (a) Critically reflect upon what has been achieved and receive feedback from policymakers and civil society, (b) provide a platform to the winners of our open call on gender equality to share reflections from their experience on what the CSS approach can achieve, and (c) capture all highlights of three years of diverse activities in the strive to create a CSS approach in an easily accessible and informative short film.

- On October 18, GIG hosted an online panel discussion in which we unpacked several critical learnings from our CoAct experiences and received feedback from leading civil society members and policymakers.
- On October 19, OKF hosted a panel discussion, 'Citizen Social Science and Civic Organisations - Which tools for which results', in which the Open Call on gender equality mentors and the winners shared their experiences about this unique mentoring format.
- On October 20, CoAct partners hosted a live streaming event for the production 'CoAct - 3 years of research and learning', followed by a public online discussion forum for the audience to share their thoughts, ask questions, and further connect. The dissemination page was: <https://coactproject.eu/events/final-event-week/>

With these final events, CoAct achieved to engage its already-grown community as well as new participants. Especially the critical self-reflection on CoAct's learnings and the invitation to policy and civil society experts for an open and transparent feedback session attracted various stakeholder groups to engage. Other stakeholders who considered CoAct's CSS

approach a crucial contribution and worth building further activities got in contact with CoAct researchers during the event days. For instance, a professor from the International Institute of Social Studies at the University of Rotterdam was keen on learning from our experiences and exploring further opportunities to expand the CSS approach. The recorded online sessions are available on YouTube and CoACT's website video section and, on December 2022, reached 251 people.

See Annexe 1 for the complete list of events and their reach.

5 Scientific publications

CoAct's scientific publications reached up to 460 thousand people, the majority of EU and international researchers. Three publications are responsible for the vast majority of the target audience.

The most significant one is the article compilation book "The Science of Citizen Science", an open-access publication providing a unique overview of citizen science. Up to now, it has 428.000 views. And two articles, "Participation and Co-creation in Citizen Science" and "Citizen Social Science: New and Established Approaches to Participation in Social Research", have 16.000 and 17.000 views, respectively.

CoAct's scientific researches have open access, and a complete list of published papers is on Annexe 1 and our website (<https://coactproject.eu/open-citizen-social-science-zenodo/>).

6 Online innovative materials

6.1 Videos

Movies are a terrific method to bring attention to a worthy cause. They allow imparting information about subjects significant to CoAct project. In addition, videos aid in spreading awareness and demonstrating the significance of the action, getting the attention it deserves and making people experience life-changing moments through watching them. Likewise, during the COVID-19 pandemic, online videos have become viral, from panels and debates to music concerts and dancing tik-tokers.

CoAct consortium partners produced 42 videos, from manuals and tutorials to online debates, conferences, and documentaries. One can find 37 videos on the website at <https://coactproject.eu/videos/>, and more are on the CSS summer school page <https://coactproject.eu/open-materials-citizen-social-science-school/>.

The complete video list and reach are in Annexe 1.

6.2 Flyer

Partners used a printed flyer to present the project at the beginning of the project. It included a snippet about CoAct, R&I Actions location and contact channels (website, social media and email). On its back, workshop participants can write ideas or answer questions in lines printed

for this purpose. Considering COVID restrictions, CoAct consortium partners shared the digital version of the flyer with participants at online conferences, workshops and meetings.

Figure 15. CoAct Flyer

Communication and dissemination actions included creating and sharing digital flyers containing infographics, like the ones for the Gender Equality Open Calls and The Hangout Series, among others. They are available online, on the website and social media cards.

Figure 16. Gender Equality Open Calls and CoAct Hangouts 2022 Flyers

6.3 Brochure and posters

CoAct created six brochures as projects' outcomes. They are four Policy Briefs and two Whitepapers. Policy Briefs provide policymakers, civil society organisations and research-performing institutions with recommendations on how to use Citizen Social Science to support and shape social change, laying out the benefits and challenges experienced by the consortium partners.

One of the Whitepapers presents a set of 6 core principles identified as highly relevant for implementing co-evaluation practices in citizen social science. It intends to guide the participatory approach to project evaluation and to sharpen the focus for impact assessment. The other Whitepaper aims to support civic organisations using Citizen Social Science (CSS) methods for gender-based projects.

The brochures are available on the Policy Briefs and Whitepapers page on the website at https://coactproject.eu/category/resources/policybriefs_whitepapers/. Furthermore, CoAct consortium partner ZSI distributed 20 printed copies of the Co-evaluation Whitepaper during the ECSA 2022 conference.

Two posters were designed to showcase the Platform co-developed to support Environmental Justice R&I actions in Buenos Aires, Argentina. They are 1,90m high and describe how to use the platform. The posters lie on the walls of San Martín University in Buenos Aires. They are available at <https://coactproject.eu/blog/environmental-justice-in-argentina-new-poster-launched/>.

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The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 873048

Figure 18. CoAct Poster for Environmental Justice R&I Action (Argentina)

OPR **CoAct**

¿Qué pasa, Riachuelo?

CALIDAD DE AGUA

¿Qué pasa, Riachuelo? (OPR) es una herramienta de ciencia ciudadana social. A través del mapeo colaborativo permite organizar, sistematizar y compartir las visiones y el conocimiento acumulado a lo largo de los años por organizaciones sociales, científicas y actores sociales. Fue desarrollado entre distintas personas y organizaciones interesadas en la justicia ambiental en la CUENCA MATANZA-RIACHUELO.

¿Quiénes pueden participar?
Cualquier persona con experiencia y conocimiento sobre un tema puede participar activamente en el proyecto.

¿Qué es la ciencia ciudadana social?
Investigación participativa en el territorio por un grupo de ciudadanos que comparten una preocupación social para proponer medidas científicamente fundamentadas para promover el cambio social.

¿Qué entendemos por calidad del agua?
Estado de las características químicas, físicas y biológicas del agua. La calidad del agua depende del uso que se le da. Por ejemplo, puede ser apta para alguna actividad pero no para beber. La plataforma OPR permite registrar lo que se observa en la superficie o cercanos de los cuerpos de agua de la Cuenca.

ASPECTOS SOBRE LA CALIDAD DEL AGUA:

- 1. Estado del agua:**
La turbidez es causada por pequeños partículas sólidas, en suspensión o disueltas.
Agua clara / Agua turbia / Turbia / Muy turbia / Otro.
Ejemplos: LIMPIA / TURBIA.
- 2. Color:**
Son variados los colores que puede adoptar, entre ellos se encuentran los siguientes:
Sin color / Verde (debido a la posible presencia de algas) / Marrón (debido a la presencia de sedimentos en suspensión) / Gris (aguas grises o descargas domésticas) / Negro (presencia de hidrocarburos) / Rojo (presencia de aguas residuales de la industria química o posible presencia de agua) / Otro color.
- 3. Fuentes potencial de contaminación cercana:**
Existen diferentes tipos de fuentes de contaminación. Entre son algunos ejemplos: Industrial, Doméstica, Fertilizantes, Pesticidas, Ceresales, Cárnicas.
- 4. Presencia de vegetación en las márgenes y en el cuerpo de agua:** Sí/No
- 5. Presencia de fauna:** Sí/No
- 6. Presencia de olores:** Sí/No
- 7. Materiales flotantes:** Plásticos, Restos de vegetación, Paños, Cables y textiles, Madera, Voluminosos, Otros.

¿Qué entendemos por Hidrometeorología?
La hidrometeorología es la disciplina que estudia el ciclo del agua entre la superficie de la Tierra y la atmósfera, en sus distintos etapas: evaporación, condensación, precipitación, intersección de la lluvia, infiltración y escurrimiento superficial.

Aspectos de la situación hidrometeorológica:

- 1. Situación hidrológica actual:**
Nivel del agua: Alto (cerca del desborde o desbordado) / Medio (niveles mayores a los habituales pero que están lejos de la posibilidad de desborde).
- 2. Situación hidrológica previa:**
Estado del tiempo en días anteriores al reporte: ¿En los días previos o durante el momento de la observación existieron vientos fuertes (tormentas)? - Sí/No / ¿Llovió en los días previos o durante el momento de la observación? - Sí/No / ¿Qué tipo de lluvia se produjo? / Involúna / Brevísima intensa breve / Lluvia intensa sostenida.

¿Cómo podemos participar en la investigación sobre la calidad del agua?
A través de observaciones in situ de cuerpos de agua, como ríos, canales y arroyos, y también de partes vitales del sistema de desagües. En la Cuenca para compartir experiencias en OPR CALIDAD DEL AGUA, podemos encontrar información para identificar situaciones vinculadas a la calidad del agua y realizar un reporte en la plataforma ¿Qué pasa, Riachuelo? Puedes descargar la guía de <https://quepasaenriachuelo.fam.org.ar/>. Además, si la registras en OPR, podrás subir fotografías, documentos y videos.

¿Para qué puede servir la información generada entre todos y todas?

- Los datos serán vitales la situación de la calidad del agua superficial en todo lo cuencas, incluso en zonas no monitoreadas por AGUAMAT.
- Para las comunidades, el involucramiento permite comprender mejor la dinámica de la cuenca e identificar situaciones críticas.
- Para las autoridades, los datos permiten evaluar la efectividad de los programas de gestión y caracterizar los puntos contaminados en fuentes específicas o desconocidas.
- Para la investigación científica, los datos generados por las ciudadanas permiten ampliar el análisis de la evolución temporal y espacial de los parámetros de calidad del agua.

Logos: European Union, CENIT, FARM, Ministerio de Recursos Naturales.

<https://mapaqr.fam.org.ar/>

A magnificent poster was designed for Mental Health R&I actions, describing the co-researchers' journey. The illustrator drew the images in real time during an after-research interview.

Figure 19. Detail of the poster – Mental Health R&I Action (Barcelona)

The poster can be accessed at <https://coactproject.eu/blog/the-co-researchers-journey-in-coact-for-mental-health/>

6.4 CSS Global Perspectives

The Global Perspectives Publication is the critical reflection of a group of global makers and innovators on the Citizen Social Science concept. These actors, who are all deeply rooted in projects fostering local engagement in change processes, raised some critical concerns, ranging from western framings of science to the often somewhat limited enactment of actual participation, as in local ownership. The publication is online on CoAct website at <https://coactproject.eu/css-global-perspectives/>

The five topics are:

- Locally driven protocols and local traditions
- The Ownership of Science
- Decolonising our educational/institutional influences
- Overcoming false representation in participatory processes
- Ethical standard setting

With every topic, a driving question showcased how those issues are addressed in people's local community work or through think pieces that provide a more overarching reflection. The contributions received from numerous actors, mainly from Latin American, African and South East Asian contexts, guide rethinking institutional silos and provide concrete examples and lessons learned from how to address those issues in practice. In this way, Global Perspectives offers various contributions to sustainability:

1. It broads the concept of Citizen Social Science by demonstrating how local engagement in scientific processes is done around the world
2. It demonstrates how CSS is narrowing itself in an academic conceptualisation of science.
3. It provides examples from different socio-political contexts, thus diversifying and helping non-western actors to identify with the concept.

Shaping the CSS approach in a participatory manner requires engaging a broad and diverse community in the entire debate. In this way, CoAct community gradually strengthened itself

through the tools used for community building, and community participation embraced CSS to flourish inside and outside academia. Furthermore, it provided an inclusive approach to the concept, openly and equally acknowledging different communities of experts and their crucial roles.

Local contexts and interests drove community participation to emancipate and disseminate the CSS approach beyond CoAct, crafting a community that will be owned and carried on beyond CoAct's project timebound. Moreover, creating a CSS community that collectively holds and shapes the CSS approach is intrinsically connected to the values CoAct stands for.

7 Printed products

The COVID-19 pandemic urged the consortium partners to postpone paper-printed material for future in-person meetings. The rationale for this decision was to avoid piling printed materials and being unable to distribute them for just a couple of months (without being sure when it would be). Still, considerations about sustainability and the world environment rose during the pandemic, pointing to the intense harms of mass media printed papers. Furthermore, communication materials for CoAct actions become digital and online, as most things during the lockdowns.

Flyers created and printed before the lockdowns were distributed at the beginning and end of the project and intensively used in online campaigns and blog posts. On a local level, Mental Health Care R&I Action created and printed a research notebook distributed at the kick-off of a co-creation session with Co-Researchers. They've got 30 notebooks in total.

Figure 20. Research Notebook R&I Action Mental Health Care

In Vienna, the consortium partner distributed ten printed flyers to young co-researchers at the Introduction Day in the AusbildungFit Institution. Furthermore, UNIVIE printed essential documentation called the 'Partizipative Forschung zur AusBildung bis 18' report in small numbers and distributed it to Knowledge Coalition members and researchers visiting UNIVIE's exhibition. It is available at <https://zenodo.org/record/7390893#.Y6Q-K-KZOE.s>.

Finally, ZSI partners distributed 20 printed versions of the Whitepaper on Citizen Social Science Evaluation during the ECSA conference in 2022.

A complete list of printed material and distribution is in Annexe 1.

8 Dissemination activities numbers

During the last 36 months, CoAct delivered the Citizen Social Science concepts and practices to more than 1,6 million people, 1 million (65%) from civil society and almost 500 thousand (28%) EU and international researchers worldwide. This analysis used several tools to grab these numbers. First and foremost, the consortium partners used a collective data spreadsheet to log their press, media and social media publications constantly, add scientific papers when published, and report on events organised and co-organised and printed materials distributed. Moreover, partners reported the number of participants for each activity correspondingly.

When activities had the digital as a medium, this analysis considered numbers and data provided by the respective tool, like the number of visitors or views. However, when none of the techniques succeeded in gathering numbers, it added a value based on an average of the lowest reach in the same categories of actions. So, for example, even though some scientific papers reported from 16000 to 17000 views on their published pages, similar scientific articles published on similar platforms, but without a public report on page access, the analysis considered and added a value of reach = 50. This minimum average allows a way of assuming how actions reached the target public.

Figure 21. Target Groups reached

Dissemination's second phase (April 2021 to December 2022) reached most of the public. Scientific publications in the first phase (January 2020 to March 2021) delivered CoAct's ideas to most of the acquired target audience.

Figure 22. Total estimated reached per phase

Social media channels, scientific papers and actions on non-scientific media channels, like TV programs and podcasts, were responsible for most of this target group's reach. Newsletters and the website also contributed to the high number of people reached but demanded more actions to be done.

Table 3 – Number of people reached by activities per phase

Number of Persons reached by activity		
Activity	Phase 1	Phase 2
Popularised publication	2,160	380,450
Press release	2,045	250
Social Media	199,425	251,673
Video / Film	1,868	2,526
Website	10,851	95,685
Other	25,949	99,464
Flyer	45	10
Scientific Papers	466,500	1,053
Events organised	919	1,116
Events participated	23,207	4,188
Material Distribution	780	260

Figure 23. Reach by activity

A detailed and comprehensive data analysis on all CoAct's Communication and Dissemination Actions is in Annexe 1.

9 Conclusion and outlook – building a community of practice

The objectives of CoAct's communication and dissemination activities were:

- To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle.
- To increase scientific literacy, skills, competence, and public awareness regarding science.
- To disseminate CoAct and build a sustainable citizen social science community of practice.

The consortium worked towards achieving these objectives, facing and overcoming the unpredictable pandemic with creativity in its actions. Communication and dissemination campaigns met expected KPIs, even outnumbering them. The number of webinars, community hangouts and blog series, gender equality open calls, the available citizen social science toolkit, informative videos, scientific papers published, and many other activities all emphasise those efforts. In addition, they could engage civil society in R&I initiatives while increasing scientific literacy, skills, competence, and public awareness regarding science and citizen science. CoAct's dissemination and communications strategies gradually raise knowledge about citizen social science in its target groups, as planned.

But, the most crucial detail is that, during the project, CoAct emphasised activities to build and support sustainable Citizen Social Science communities of practice that are inclusive, diverse, and transdisciplinary. A set of participatory activities gradually built this community:

- Open calls for videos: an initial step, providing a platform for CSS initiatives to present their work and for the different initiatives to learn about and from each other. Answering questions like "What does CSS mean for you?", "What would you need to make a CSS approach meaningful to civil society?" and "How would a CSS community of practitioners from civil society and academia ideally look like?" the contributions are on the CoAct website (<https://coactproject.eu/community-videos-contribution/>).
- Citizen Social Science Meetup: an active meeting of global citizen scientists around the topic. It was a basis for gathering proposals and suggestions to establish a community. One can find the complete documentation and the meetup recording here: <https://coactproject.eu/news/a-new-family-is-born-join-coacts-opencitizensocialscience-community/>.
- Citizen Social Science Community chat group: an outcome from the prior action (Citizen Social Science Meetup), the chat group is an active message group hosted on [Signal](#), a privacy-oriented and open-source communication tool. The group is an environment for a low barrier, instant exchange of thoughts, events, and materials, with 61 members from around the globe.

- Community Hangouts: A series of nine online community meetings that contributed to shaping a global bottom-up perspective on how science should/is be thought of and addressed, and how inclusive, bottom-up practices are enabled in the most diverse contexts worldwide. With participants from all continents, it highlighted best practices and lessons learned. Community Hangouts were a sharing knowledge space to support other actors shaping their respective communities while learning from their experiences.

Together with events participation and the already active academic community around its scientific papers, CoAct believes Citizen Social Science studies can grow from and take root from this Horizon 2020 project on the grounds of Science and Open Science.

10 Annexe 1

Communication and Dissemination outreach activities

Report on Dissemination and Communication activities and reach

Specify the number of Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the project for each of the following categories

Category	January 2020 to March 2021 - Phase 1		April 2021 to December 2022 - Phase 2	
	January 2020 to March 2021 - Phase 1	April 2021 to December 2022 - Phase 2	January 2020 to March 2021 - Phase 1	April 2021 to December 2022 - Phase 2
Organisation of a Conference	2	8	2	8
Organisation of a Workshop	3	24	1	2
Press release	1	2	3	16
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	0	1	0	1
Exhibition	0	1	0	1
Flyer	2	1	1	1
Training	1	1	1	1
Social Media	216	334	28	121
Website	28	121	19	39
Participation to a Conference	19	39	1	5
Participation to a Workshop	1	30	4	30
Participation to an Event (other)	4	5	12	30
Video/Film				
Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)				
Other			21	30

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of all dissemination and communication activities, in each of the following categories

Category	Absolute	Relative
Vulnerable citizens	1,250	0.08
Civil society	1,070,491	64.71
Local administrations	2,228	0.13
EU and worldwide researchers	498,737	30.15
International networks/associations	76,972	4.65
EU policy makers	4,596	0.28

Total Estimated Reach 1,654,274

Total Estimated Reach by Phase	Phase 1	Phase 2
	733,749	836,675

Activity	Number of Persons reached by activity	
	Phase 1	Phase 2
Popularised publication	2,160	380,450
Press release	2,045	250
Social Media	199,425	251,673
Video / Film	1,868	2,526
Website	10,851	95,685
Other	25,949	99,464
Flyer	45	10
Scientific Papers	466,500	1,053
Events organised	919	1,116
Material Distribution	23,207	4,188
Events organised jointly with other EU project(s)	780	260

Press and Media Outreach

This is a tool to monitor partners communication and dissemination activities during the whole project. When a CoAct partner releases or carries out a specific action (for example: blogs, press releases, press article, flyers, videos/film), podcast, poster, exhibition, social media post on their institutional channels, newsletter, publication on their website, etc.) a new entry on this excel log must be added including some basic information about the action made.

Partner - Universitat de Barcelona

Nr.	Type of Publication/Activiti	Title/Description	Link	Date	Location	Partner	Language	/ activities in of reach	Target group	Others (specify)
1	Populaised publication	Podcast	https://blogs.uoc.edu/informatica/despachos-42-decidim-fest-revolucio	26/11/2021	Podcast	UB	Cat	1	100 Civil society	Podcast
2	Populaised publication	El projecte 'CoActuem' crea un xatbot a Telegram per	https://diarieladidacapat.cat/le-proiecte-coactuem-crea-un-xatbot	28/11/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	1000 Vulnerable citizen	Piece on news inside the "Disability Diary"
3	Populaised publication	Federació Salut Mental Catalunya llança un chatbot	https://www.discardes.es/actualidad/2021/12/federacio-salut-mental	13/12/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	1000 Vulnerable citizen	News bulletin for people having a disability
4	Populaised publication	SMCY UB crea un "chatbot" de salud mental que a	https://www.europapress.es/catalunya/noticia-smc-ub-crea-chatbot	15/12/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	1000 Civil society	Piece of news from Europapress
5	Populaised publication	Un 'xatbot' per investigar com afrontar millor els pro	https://www.rtve.es/play/audiios/generacion-yo-coact-uamos-salud-m	18/12/2021	Printed+online	UB	Cat	1	130000 Civil society	Printed publication in "Ara" newspaper, one of the most readen
6	Populaised publication	Ràdio 3 (Radio Televisión Española)	https://www.rtve.es/play/audiios/generacion-yo-coact-uamos-salud-m	20/12/2021	Radio	UB	Cat	1	50000 Civil society	Radio 3
7	Populaised publication	Ràdio 4 (Radio Televisión Española)	https://www.rtve.es/play/audiios/generacion-yo-coact-uamos-salud-m	22/12/2021	Radio	UB	Cat	1	50000 Civil society	Ràdio 4, participació de una persona coinvestigadora
8	Populaised publication	Com funciona el xatbot CoActuem per la Salut Mental	https://xarxanet.org/informatic/recursos/com-funciona-el-xatbot-coa	22/12/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	150 Civil society	
9	Populaised publication	La Xarxa TV / Connectat	http://www.alacarta.cat/connectat/?all/un-xatbot-per-a-avancar-en-la-mil	19/01/2022	TV	UB	Cat	1	10000 Civil society	Local TV
10	Populaised publication	Badalona TV / Badalona Tres60	https://youtu.be/w7F6eQbVt4	19/01/2022	TV	UB	Cat	1	10000 Civil society	Local TV
11	Populaised publication	TV Hospitalaet / Informatiu	https://bit.ly/3B2Ms1b	04/02/2022	TV	UB	Cat	1	5000 Civil society	local TV, participació de una persona coinvestigadora
12	Populaised publication	Neix un xatbot col·laboratiu de salut mental	https://www.cma.cat/catradio/alacarta/programa/neix-un-xatbot-collab	07/02/2022	Radio	UB	Cat	1	20000 Civil society	Catalunya Ràdio
13	Populaised publication	Mataró Ràdio. Programa Valors a l'alta	http://mataroaudiovisual.alacarta.cat/valors-alta/capitol/vlors-a-lalta-210	21/02/2022	Radio	UB	Cat	1	3000 Civil society	Mataró Ràdio
Reach Phase 2: 280400 Actions Phase 1: 0 Actions Phase 2: 13										
14	Press release	Press release to local and national journalists	https://us15.campaign-archive.com/?u=a42117cd4b7d4c2969857f6cbb	01/12/2021	Online	UB	Cat/Cast	1	120 Civil society	Journalists
15	Press release	Press release to local and national journalists	https://us15.campaign-archive.com/?u=a42117cd4b7d4c2969857f6cbb	27/12/2021	Online	UB	Cat/Cast	1	120 Civil society	Journalists
Reach Phase 1 0 Actions Phase 1: 0 Actions Phase 2: 2										
16	Social Media	43 Twitter posts (@opensystemsUB) with reads for	https://twitter.com/OpensystemsUB	01/01/2021	Online	UB	Cat/Cast/Eng	43	52900 Civil society	ALL TARGETS
17	Social Media	94 Twitter posts (@opensystemsUB) from 01.01.2021	https://twitter.com/OpensystemsUB	01/01/2021	Online	UB	Cat/Cast/Eng/	94	70100 Civil society	ALL TARGETS
Reach Phase 1 123000 Actions Phase 1: 137 Actions Phase 2: 0										
18	Video / Film	CoActuem per la Salut Mental	https://vimeo.com/472725854	01/10/2020	Online	UB	Cat	1	200 Civil society	
19	Video / Film	CoActuamos para la Salud Mental	https://vimeo.com/472726098	01/10/2020	Online	UB	Cat	1	80 Civil society	
20	Video / Film	CoAct for Mental Health	https://vimeo.com/472726240	01/10/2020	Online	UB	Eng	1	50 Civil society	
21	Video / Film	Unxarx-te al xatbot CoActuem per la Salut Mental	https://vimeo.com/649395458	01/10/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	650 Civil society	
22	Video / Film	Unete al chatbot CoActuamos por la Salud Mental	https://vimeo.com/639905883	01/10/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	120 Civil society	
23	Video / Film	Join CoAct for Mental Health chatbot	https://vimeo.com/639902984	01/10/2021	Online	UB	Eng	1	60 Civil society	
24	Video / Film	Tretan Sie dem CoAct für Mentale Gesundheit Chatb	https://vimeo.com/639907872	01/10/2021	Online	UB	De	1	50 Civil society	
Reach Phase 1 330 Actions Phase 1: 3 Actions Phase 2: 4										
25	Website	CoAct, Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collect	https://www.ub.edu/opensystems/projects/coact/	30/04/2020	Online	UB	Cat/Cast/Eng	1	300 EU and worldwide	Civil Society
26	Website	CoAct (Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collect	https://ciencia-ciudadana.es/proyecto-coact-co-designing-citizens-s	01/10/2020	Online	UB	Cat	1	200 National institutions	
27	Website	CoActuamos para la Salud Mental	https://ciencia-ciudadana.es/proyecto-coact-uamos-para-la-salud-m	01/10/2020	Online	UB	Cat	1	200 National institutions	
28	Website	Open access publication of a book on citizen science	https://www.ub.edu/web/ub/en/menu_etnies/noticies/2021/01/09/8	14/01/2022	Online	UB	Cat/Cast/Eng	1	1000 EU researchers	
29	Website	First citizen science chatbot opens up research on m	https://www.ub.edu/web/ub/en/menu_etnies/noticies/2022/11/03/9	18/11/2022	Online	UB	Cat/Cast/Eng	1	1000 EU and worldwide researchers	
Reach Phase 1 700 Actions Phase 1: 3 Actions Phase 2: 2										
30	Other	CoActFrenaLaCurva project in EU-Citizen.science new	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2020/07/26/coactfrenalacurva-project	28/07/2020	Online	UB	Eng	1	500 EU and worldwide researchers	
31	Other	ECSA newsletter: Shaping citizen social science toget	https://mailchi.mp/907661f6420/ecca-newsletter-october-2020?e=3	08/10/2020	Online	UB	Eng	1	1000 EU and worldwide researchers	
32	Other	Una dècada de ciència ciutadana en apoy del desat	https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/sociedad/2020/10/08/una-decada-d	08/10/2020	Printed+online	UB	Cat	1	300 Civil society	
33	Other	IDIAPGol participa al projecte CoActuem per la Sal	https://www.idiapgol.org/index.php/ca/actualitat/noticies/1590-coac	31/12/2021	Corporate web	UB	Cat	1	150 National institutio	KC Member website
34	Other	CoAct, una iniciativa global financada per la Unió Eu	https://diciencia.cat/ca/details/Noticia/coact	22/12/2021	Corporate web	UB	Cat	1	50 Local administrat	Government of Catalonia website
35	Other	Federació Salut Mental Catalunya llança un chatbot	https://consaludmental.org/sala-prensa/federacio-salut-mental-catalu	07/12/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	50 Vulnerable citizen	News bulletin from the Spanish Federation of Mental Health
36	Other	CoActuem per millorar les xarxes de suport social en	https://www.hospitalbenitornell.org/ca/complex-assistencial/comun	01/01/2021	Online	UB	Cat	1	1000 EU and worldwide researchers	News bulletin from the mental health center, member of the KC
37	Other	ECSA newsletter: Open Materials of the CoAct Citize	https://mailchi.mp/2c687746b50/feb2022?e=325b66749a	01/02/2022	Online	UB	Eng	1	2000 EU and worldwide researchers	
38	Other	CoActuem: ciència ciutadana i salut mental	https://info.comunicacio.ub.edu/vl/b2399-7ce24c239171b708874237	23/11/2022	Online	UB	Cat	1	3300 EU and worldwide researchers	
Reach Phase 2 1800 Actions Phase 1: 3 Actions Phase 2: 6										
Partner - Zentrum für Soziale Innovation										
Nr.	Type of Publication/Activiti	Title/Description	Link	Date	Location	Partner	Language	/ activities in of reach	Target group	Others (specify)
1	Populaised publication	Citizen Social Science: Probleme durch Partizipation	https://science.apa.at/power-search/8533791389565313339	15/12/2022	online	ZSI	German	1	20000 Civil Society, International Networks	
Reach Phase 1 0 Actions Phase 1: 0 Actions Phase 2: 1										
2	Press Release	Contribution to Science of Citizen Science Book	https://science.apa.at/power-search/72533873133860786059	05/02/2021	online	ZSI	German	1	2000 EU and worldwide	Civil Society; International Networks
Reach Phase 1 2000 Actions Phase 1: 1 Actions Phase 2: 0										
3	Social Media	CFP-Special Issue Participatory Evaluation in Citizen S	https://twitter.com/fevalhangen	29/04/2021	online	ZSI	English	1	500 EU and worldwide researchers, CSOs	

86	Other	Email List: invitation to Participatory Evaluation Event (02./03. February 2022)		30/11/2021	Online (Email)	UnViE	German	1	2845	Civil society			
87	Other	Email List: invitation to Train-the-Trainers: Actionbound zum Thema Ausbildung und Beruf		30/12/2021	Online (Email)	UnViE	German	1	2945	Civil society			
87	Other	CoAct Projektpresentation: Partizipative Forschung	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ag30PbD88	16/12/2022	Online (Youtube)	UnViE	German	1	4	Civil society			
88	Other	Paneldiskussion: Sozialpolitische Veränderung durch	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=az86jVx85	16/12/2022	Online (Youtube)	UnViE	German	1	4	EU and worldwide researchers			
				Reich phase 1	2946				17593			1	Actions Phase 2: 9
Partner - Fachhochschule Potsdam													
Nr.	Type of Publication/Activi	Title/Description	Link	Date	Location	Partner	Language	/ activities	m of reach	Target group	Others (specify)		
1	Press Release	Transnationales Bürgerforschungsprojekt „CoAct“ ge	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/informieren/aktuelles/news-detailansicht	28/02/2020	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	German	1	1500	Civil society			
2	Press Release	FHP-Forschungsteam an Organisation der Citizen Sci	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/informieren/aktuelles/news-detailansicht	14/07/2020	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	German	1	1500	Civil society			
3	Press Release	Transnationales Bürgerforschungsprojekt „CoAct“ ge	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/informieren/aktuelles/news-detailansicht	28/07/2020	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	German	1	1500	Civil society			
4	Press Release	Knowledge for Change	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/informieren/aktuelles/news-detailansicht	28/07/2020	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	German	1	1500	Civil society			
5	Press Release	Co-designing Citizen Science for Collective Acti	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/informieren/aktuelles/news-detailansicht	22/12/2020	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	German	1	1500	Civil society			
6	Press Release	FH Potsdam und CoAct bereiten Ausschreibung vor	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/informieren/aktuelles/news-detailansicht	19/03/2021	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	German	1	1500	Civil society			
7	Press Release	Forschungsförderung für Women of Color in Berlin-	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/informieren/aktuelles/news-detailansicht	17/01/2022	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	German	1	1500	Civil society			
				Reich phase 1	9000				1500			6	Actions Phase 2: 1
8	Website	CoAct Co-designing Citizen Science for Collect	https://www.fh-potsdam.de/en/studieren/fachbereiche/sozial-und-bil	14/02/2020	Potsdam, Germa	FHP	English + German		386	EU and worldwide researchers			
				Reich phase 1	386				0			1	Actions Phase 2: 0
Partner - Universidad Nacional de General San Martín													
Nr.	Type of Publication/Activi	Title/Description	Link	Date	Location	Partner	Language	/ activities	m of reach	Target group	Others (specify)		
1	Social Media	Proyecto CoAct!	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1217146667264331777	14/01/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	423	Civil society			
2	Social Media	Proyecto CoAct de Ciencia Ciudadana	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1224383512360472579	03/02/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	3207	Civil society			
3	Social Media	Presentación en #CitiSci2020	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1303318034690576390	08/09/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	471	EU and worldwide			
4	Social Media	CoAct Riachuelo en Citizen Science SDG Conference	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1316441076803215361	14/10/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	260	Local administrat	National institutions, local researchers		
5	Social Media	CoAct Riachuelo en Citizen Science SDG Conference	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/photos/a.8493948817386733/	14/10/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	57	Local administrat	National institutions, local researchers		
6	Social Media	Valeria Arza y Guillermina Actis participaron de la #C	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/posts/3750343681643764	16/10/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	92	Local administrat	National institutions, local researchers		
7	Social Media	Valeria Arza participará del Seminario de Ciencia Ciu	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/posts/378089755358212	26/10/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	96	Local administrat	National institutions, local researchers		
8	Social Media	Valeria Arza presenta la iniciativa "Ciencia ciudadana	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1321805346537693184	29/10/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	215	Local administrat	National institutions, local researchers		
9	Social Media	Valeria Arza en el seminario Ciencia ciudadana para	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/13278593067621969994	29/10/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	304	Local administrat	National institutions, local researchers		
10	Social Media	Primer taller de co-diseño del proyecto CoAct Riachuelo	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/photos/a.8493948817386733/	03/11/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	675	Civil society	Vulnerable citizens, local administrators, local researchers		
11	Social Media	Primer taller de co-diseño del proyecto CoAct Riach	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/13236909097546588817	03/11/2020	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	2068	Civil society	Vulnerable citizens, local administrators, local researchers		
12	Social Media	Difusión blog post: Wrapping up Co Act Riachuelo's	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/posts/40533804880067417	03/02/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	54	Civil society	local researchers		
13	Social Media	Difusión nota web: Un año de CoAct Riachuelo: co-d	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/posts/49586571793477457	04/02/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	40	Civil society	local researchers		
14	Social Media	Difusión nota web: Un año de CoAct Riachuelo: co-d	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/135139102450913288	04/02/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	277	Civil society	local researchers		
15	Social Media	Difusión de Timeline de la web de Coact global	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1367679558625750818	04/03/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	266	Civil society	local researchers		
16	Social Media	Difusión video Coact Global	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/137982383542436225	07/04/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	377	Civil society	local researchers		
17	Social Media	Coact Summer school	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/14381682240716748813520	15/09/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	72	EU and worldwide	local researchers		
18	Social Media	ig interview dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/825937867417708/posts/473096484024817709/	17/09/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	639	Civil society	local researchers		
19	Social Media	ig interview dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/825937867417708/posts/4897878416890811/	04/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	155	Civil society	local researchers		
20	Social Media	ig interview dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/825937867417708/posts/4957565273520	08/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	155	Civil society	local researchers		
21	Social Media	ig interview dissemination	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/14584267198414970957520	10/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	70	Civil society	local researchers		
22	Social Media	ig interview dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/825937867417708/posts/49343783165731911/	10/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	217	Civil society	local researchers		
23	Social Media	ig interview dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/825937867417708/posts/49034418230001011/	10/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	66	Civil society	local researchers		
24	Social Media	Coact included in a UNDP publication: mapping envil	https://www.facebook.com/825937867417708/posts/49702725979381511/	15/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	125	Local administrat	local researchers		
25	Social Media	ig interview dissemination	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/14603170067130450007520	15/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	440	Civil society	local researchers		
26	Social Media	ig interview	https://www.instagram.com/p/CWHFQmBkVW/	17/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	63	Civil society	local researchers		
27	Social Media	Blog post dissemination	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1461777039007006787520	19/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	122	Civil society	local researchers		
28	Social Media	Blog post dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/825937867417708/posts/49343783165731911/	19/11/2021	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	51	Civil society	local researchers		
29	Social Media	Tweet: Blog post dissemination	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/14896150060852691720ct=HH	04/02/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	78	Civil society	local researchers		
30	Social Media	FB post: Blog post dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/posts/52310211935759987_e070702/	07/02/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	115	Civil society	local researchers		
31	Social Media	FB post: Lecture, led by Coact members at UNSA	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/photos/a.8493948817386733/	16/02/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	89	Civil society	local researchers		
32	Social Media	Tweet: Lecture led by Coact members at UNSAM	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/14940266878764072520ct=HH	16/02/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	244	Civil society	local researchers		
33	Social Media	FB post: Coact is mentioned in a open-science comm	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/posts/5410417148969724	11/04/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	76	Civil society	local researchers		
34	Social Media	Tweet: Coact is mentioned in a open-science comm	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1513513515053378575208_11704/	11/04/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	447	Civil society	local researchers		
35	Social Media	Tweet: Coact website launching	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/152991205827951413835208_2605/	26/05/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	198	Civil society	local researchers		
36	Social Media	Fb post: Coact website launching	https://www.facebook.com/fund_cent/posts/55327352956287852	26/05/2022	Buenos Aires		Spanish	1	102	Civil society	local researchers		
37	Social Media	Tweet: Valeria Arza represents CoAct Riachuelo at th	https://twitter.com/fund_cent/status/1531325410625072248	30/05/2022	Barcelona		Spanish	1	81	Civil society	local researchers		

38	Social Media	Fb post: Valeria Arza represents CoAct Riachuelo at https://www.facebook.com/fund.centri.posts/5549831531694961	30/05/2022	Barcelona	Spanish	1	123	Civil society	local researchers			
39	Social Media	Fb post: sobre un taller: #CoAct Riachuelo en Avellan https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0z1gQeTAId	31/05/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	110	Civil society	local researchers			
40	Social Media	Tweet: sobre un taller: #CoAct Riachuelo en Avellan https://twitter.com/centri/status/153172163998864672	31/05/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	75	Civil society	local researchers			
41	Social Media	Fb post: Avances de #CoAct Justicia ambiental en el https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0c17wZ0vUj	02/06/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	94	Civil society	local researchers			
42	Social Media	Tweet: Avances de #CoAct Justicia ambiental en el https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/153238094989524160	02/06/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	70	Civil society	local researchers			
43	Social Media	Tweet: Programa de TV sobre ciencia ciudadana: Me https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1554496766967517184	02/08/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	324	Civil society	local researchers			
44	Social Media	Fb post: Programa de TV sobre ciencia ciudadana: Me https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid03G7h4b1	03/08/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	91	Civil society	local researchers			
45	Social Media	Fb post: #CoAct Justicia ambiental presenta la plataforma https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0z1Tn4D0z1	22/08/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	28	Civil society	local researchers			
46	Social Media	Tweet: #CoAct Justicia ambiental presenta la plataforma https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1561713239720972291	22/08/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	135	Civil society	local researchers			
47	Social Media	Tweet: Herramientas digitales para la educación ambiental https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1570047110329909248	14/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	30	Civil society	local researchers			
48	Social Media	Fb post: Herramientas digitales para la educación ambiental https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0xADWtE8v4	14/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	15	Civil society	local researchers			
49	Social Media	Tweet: un taller para elaborar propuestas didácticas https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/status/1574483899824095248	26/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	57	Civil society	local researchers			
50	Social Media	Twitter thread: UNDP: "Diálogos entre Ciencia Ciudadana https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/15748282925424636433	27/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	383	Local administration	National institutions, local researchers			
51	Social Media	Twitter thread: National Ministry of Science... "Diálogos https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/15748282925424636433	27/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	374	Local administration	National institutions, local researchers			
52	Social Media	Tweet: Taller de ciencia ciudadana para la educación https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/157520817324370176	28/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	169	Civil society	Vulnerable citizens			
53	Social Media	Tweet: Taller de ciencia ciudadana para la educación https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1575208180312775608	28/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	85	Civil society	Vulnerable citizens			
54	Social Media	Fb: Difusión nota web Taller Participación ciudadana https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0uVzQaams	28/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	22	Local administration	local researchers			
55	Social Media	Fb: Taller de ciencia ciudadana y educación ambiental https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0uVzQaams	30/09/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	56	Civil society	Vulnerable citizens			
56	Social Media	Twitter post: Dissemination CoAct Final Conference https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/15780600420007371778	06/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	140	Civil society	local researchers			
57	Social Media	Twitter post: Dissemination CoAct Final Conference https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1578060054590283776	06/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	47	Civil society	local researchers			
58	Social Media	Twitter post: Dissemination CoAct Final Conference https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1578060061041213441	06/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	49	Civil society	local researchers			
59	Social Media	Fb: Dissemination CoAct Final Conference https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0z3XAWtj	06/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	70	Civil society	local researchers			
60	Social Media	Twitter thread: Open systems UB: ECSA Conference https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1579897189870211072	07/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	125	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
61	Social Media	Fb: Participación de CoAct Justicia Ambiental en ECSA https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0z7eYcVX	11/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	332	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
62	Social Media	Twitter thread: Open systems UB: ECSA Conference https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1579901667163926529	11/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	149	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
63	Social Media	Tweet: Difusión nota web: participación de CoAct Rio https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1580555874543624197	11/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	204	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
64	Social Media	Fb: Dissemination CoAct Final Conference https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0Xk7dmvK	14/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	91	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
65	Social Media	Twitter thread: Coacter: CoAct Riachuelo en la conf https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1582085604732325888	17/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	92	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
66	Social Media	Fb: Dissemination CoAct Final Conference https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0C4VEE4mV	17/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	100	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
67	Social Media	Fb: CoAct Final Conference Valeria Arza presenta el https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0VfMRSzEvpZ	18/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	78	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
68	Social Media	Twitter thread: Coacter: Valeria Arza presenta el tr https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1582395055827355651	18/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	64	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
69	Social Media	Tweet: Valeria Arza presenta el trabajo de CoAct Jus https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1582395055827355651	18/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	108	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
70	Social Media	Tweet: Valeria Arza presenta el trabajo de CoAct Jus https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1582395055827355651	18/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	55	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
71	Social Media	Tweet: Valeria Arza presenta el trabajo de CoAct Jus https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1582395055827355651	18/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	148	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
72	Social Media	Tweet: Valeria Arza presenta el trabajo de CoAct Jus https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1582395055827355651	18/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	90	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
73	Social Media	Tweet: CoActs Final Conference Dissemination https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1582460490307235840	18/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	85	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
74	Social Media	Twitter thread: GOSH Community: Guillermo Actis https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/158572071171244032	27/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	95	EU and worldwide	International networks			
75	Social Media	Twitter thread: National Ministry of Science... Valeria https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/158715559056484868	31/10/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	326	National institute	Local administrations, local researchers			
76	Social Media	Fb: CoAct at the Official Launch of the National Citize https://www.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfbid0zWsvyQV6	01/11/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	118	National institute	Local administrations, local researchers			
77	Social Media	Twitter thread: UNDP Official Launch of the National https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/158752465837736961	02/11/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	568	National institute	Local administrations, local researchers			
78	Social Media	Twitter thread: UNDP Citizen Science Mapping: Co-A https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/158753137624633345	02/11/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	341	National institute	Local administrations, local researchers			
79	Social Media	Twitter post: The mapping of Argentine initiatives of https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/15887740710667173120	07/11/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	273	National institute	Local administrations, local researchers			
80	Social Media	Twitter thread: Guillermo Actis talks about CoAct https://twitter.com/centri_eeynunsam/status/1590001302617088001	30/11/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	47	National institute	Local administrations, local researchers			
81	Social Media	Fb post: Guillermo Actis talks about CoAct project https://m.facebook.com/centri.eeyn.unsam/posts/pfb.5084153413140	30/11/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	104	National institute	Local administrations, local researchers			
			Reach phase 1	8505	Reach Phase 2		10297	Actions Phase 1:	15	Actions Phase 2:	66	
83	Video / Film	Video: ¿Cómo impactó el proyecto de ciencia ciudadan https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mazMxEp9zUc	19/01/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	118	EU and worldwide	Civil society, local researchers			
84	Video / Film	Video: ¿Qué es la plataforma QPR? https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4fR48rJ48U	19/01/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	73	EU and worldwide	Civil society, local researchers			
85	Video / Film	Video: ¿Qué es para vos la Ciencia del Río Matanza https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5_VTnz8Jk	19/01/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	69	EU and worldwide	Civil society, local researchers			
			Reach phase 1	0	Reach Phase 2		260	Actions Phase 1:	0	Actions Phase 2:	3	
86	Website	"Ciencia ciudadana y justicia ambiental: Avanza el pr https://noticias.unsam.edu.ar/2020/12/04/ciencia-ciudadana-y-justicia	16/12/2020	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	65	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
87	Website	Blog post https://fund.centri.org.ar/conversatorio-que-es-la-ciencia-ciudadana/	19/11/2021	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	254	EU and worldwide	local researchers			
88	Website	Blog post: Segundo año de CoAct Riachuelo: co-diseñ https://fund.centri.org.ar/segundo-año-de-coact-riachuelo-co-diseñan	03/01/2022	Buenos Aires	Spanish	1	250	EU and worldwide	local researchers			

45	Social Media	Community hangout announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1381645841899921412	12/04/2021	online	GIG	English	606	International networks/associations
46	Social Media	Community hangout announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1384118846190067718	19/04/2021	online	GIG	English	363	International networks/associations
47	Social Media	Webinar: rethinking science" announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1404711871517806599575=208t	15/06/2021	online	GIG	English	529	International networks/associations
48	Social Media	webinar announcement, speaker highlight, Joana	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14069612194833715997=208t	21/06/2021	online	GIG	English	139	International networks/associations
49	Social Media	webinar announcement, speaker highlight, Khan	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14069761815644979277=208t	21/06/2021	online	GIG	English	141	International networks/associations
50	Social Media	Webinar: rethinking science" reminder	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1407278933284949622=208t	22/06/2021	online	GIG	English	1210	International networks/associations
51	Social Media	Registrations open for the CoAct CSS school amount	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14094744220298985422=208t	28/06/2021	online	GIG	English	205	International networks/associations
52	Social Media	Livestream link: webinar	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14094749991786291209=208t	28/06/2021	online	GIG	English	672	International networks/associations
53	Social Media	Open Calls on Gender Equality announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/141086097167777327=208t	02/07/2021	online	GIG	English	149	International networks/associations
54	Social Media	Gig newsletter featuring CoAct	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14261192946627221511=208t	13/08/2021	online	GIG	English	512	International networks/associations
55	Social Media	Q&A session announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14353019194850140192=208t	07/09/2021	online	GIG	English	162	International networks/associations
56	Social Media	Seeking CSOs	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1437399146987074196523=208t	13/09/2021	online	GIG	English	193	International networks/associations
57	Social Media	webinar on gender aspects in #CitizenScience and #	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/146130447814283486897=208t	18/11/2021	online	GIG	English	68	International networks/associations
58	Social Media	webinar on gender aspects in #CitizenScience and #	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/146130447814283486897=208t	18/11/2021	online	GIG	English	60	International networks/associations
59	Social Media	November hangout	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/146130447814283486897=208t	18/11/2021	online	GIG	English	63	International networks/associations
60	Social Media	Blog post on October hangout	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/146130447814283486897=208t	18/11/2021	online	GIG	English	167	International networks/associations
61	Social Media	November hangout livestream	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14652618814221353007=208t	29/11/2021	online	GIG	English	78	International networks/associations
62	Social Media	Open calls results	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/14663765990414561433=208t	02/12/2021	online	GIG	English	78	International networks/associations
63	Social Media	Coact presentation by partners	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15630586796327567377=208t	26/08/2022	online	GIG	English	761	International networks/associations
64	Social Media	Coact hangout 4 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15602575439010037777=208t	18/08/2022	online	GIG	English	61	International networks/associations
65	Social Media	Coact hangout 4 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15555951739749253147=208t	05/08/2022	online	GIG	English	81	International networks/associations
66	Social Media	Coact hangout 3 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/153956746128739456473=208t	22/06/2022	online	GIG	English	262	International networks/associations
67	Social Media	Coact hangout 3 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15377436294727393287=208t	17/06/2022	online	GIG	English	179	International networks/associations
68	Social Media	Coact hangout 3 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/153706474868832256073=208t	15/06/2022	online	GIG	English	304	International networks/associations
69	Social Media	Coact hangout 1 blog	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15192283661965598733=208t	27/04/2022	online	GIG	English	262	International networks/associations
70	Social Media	Coact hangout 1 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15167066931723253777=208t	20/04/2022	online	GIG	English	299	International networks/associations
71	Social Media	ECSA Conference	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15145912949952839733=208t	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	86	International networks/associations
72	Social Media	Shaping an inclusive "Open *Citizen *Social Science	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1514556810304573937=208t	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	78	International networks/associations
73	Social Media	Coact hangout 1 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15137662011383234627=208t	17/04/2022	online	GIG	English	342	International networks/associations
74	Social Media	Coact hangout 1 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15119796040341749787=208t	07/04/2022	online	GIG	English	749	International networks/associations
75	Social Media	Coact hangout 1 - announcement	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15119796040341749787=208t	06/04/2022	online	GIG	English	92	International networks/associations
76	Social Media	call for publications*	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/151132526616918836073=208t	31/03/2022	online	GIG	English	506	International networks/associations
77	Social Media	Coact hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/Ch2w3n-Mk5e/	18/08/2022	online	GIG	English	96	International networks/associations
78	Social Media	Coact hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/Cg4p3tYKbqg/	05/08/2022	online	GIG	English	82	International networks/associations
79	Social Media	Coact hangout 3 - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/CfG0rKtMkqJ/	22/06/2022	online	GIG	English	63	International networks/associations
80	Social Media	Coact hangout 3 - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/Ce1AhqMkMsq/	15/06/2022	online	GIG	English	56	International networks/associations
81	Social Media	Coact hangout - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/CdmQtojsZm/	16/05/2022	online	GIG	English	47	International networks/associations
82	Social Media	Coact hangout - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/Cd4f5upaq0w/	12/05/2022	online	GIG	English	44	International networks/associations
83	Social Media	Coact hangout - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/CcKv_rgsj1/	20/04/2022	online	GIG	English	54	International networks/associations
84	Social Media	ECSA Conference	https://www.instagram.com/p/Cc458YkGc9/	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	73	International networks/associations
85	Social Media	Coact 2022 hangouts schedule	https://www.instagram.com/p/CcVCi92MwUJ/	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	59	International networks/associations
86	Social Media	Coact hangout - announcement	https://www.instagram.com/p/CcUllbHMc6Z/	07/04/2022	online	GIG	English	76	International networks/associations
87	Social Media	Coact presentation by partners	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	26/08/2022	online	GIG	English	8	International networks/associations
88	Social Media	Coact hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid0pF78kUfAeLrVj	24/08/2022	online	GIG	English	43	International networks/associations
89	Social Media	Coact hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	18/08/2022	online	GIG	English	354	International networks/associations
90	Social Media	Coact hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid037788BwFwUJCqg	05/08/2022	online	GIG	English	490	International networks/associations
91	Social Media	Open publication - Gilberto, English	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid061kUUCdZENA1Vnd	21/07/2022	online	GIG	English	111	International networks/associations
92	Social Media	Coact hangout 3 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	22/06/2022	online	GIG	English	50	International networks/associations
93	Social Media	Coact hangout 3 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid0mXpDp94RNY2Vj	22/06/2022	online	GIG	English	94	International networks/associations
94	Social Media	Coact session @ re-publica	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	15/06/2022	online	GIG	English	1744	International networks/associations
95	Social Media	Coact session @ re-publica	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	09/06/2022	online	GIG	English	1	International networks/associations
96	Social Media	Coact hangout - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	18/05/2022	online	GIG	English	57	International networks/associations
97	Social Media	Coact hangout - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	16/05/2022	online	GIG	English	49	International networks/associations
98	Social Media	Coact hangout - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid041kREtUSCu97G6	12/05/2022	online	GIG	English	878	International networks/associations
99	Social Media	Forum on impact assessment in citizen science	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid02tctRr0XG6GMhH	06/05/2022	online	GIG	English	88	International networks/associations
100	Social Media	Blog about 1st coast hangout 2022	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid02RqWwX87hmkP	27/12/2022	online	GIG	English	35	International networks/associations
101	Social Media	Coact hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/posts/pfbid02RqWwX87hmkP	21/04/2022	online	GIG	English	24	International networks/associations
102	Social Media	Coact hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	20/04/2022	online	GIG	English	30	International networks/associations
103	Social Media	ECSA conference	https://www.facebook.com/weareGIG/photos/a.1589008798031005/3	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	28	International networks/associations

104	Social Media	2022 CoAct hangouts schedule	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0244ur0412X8LlKQz	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	15	International networks/associations
105	Social Media	CoAct hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid06z4ZP026CaooTbM	12/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	28	International networks/associations
106	Social Media	CoAct hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/photos/a.1589008298031005/3	07/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	91	International networks/associations
107	Social Media	Call for open applications	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0WxSGBVnNlQvR	05/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	21	International networks/associations
108	Social Media	Gig newsletter no 19	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/photos/a.1589008298031005/3	17/03/2022	online	GIG	English	1	102	International networks/associations
109	Social Media	CoAct presentation by partners	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:696882468186	26/08/2022	online	GIG	English	1	347	International networks/associations
110	Social Media	CoAct hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:696832292853	24/08/2022	online	GIG	English	1	41	International networks/associations
111	Social Media	CoAct hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:696606232971733	18/08/2022	online	GIG	English	1	42	International networks/associations
112	Social Media	CoAct hangout 4 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6961362973736	05/08/2022	online	GIG	English	1	67	International networks/associations
113	Social Media	Join the public consultation on the 6 Principles of pe	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:695881030804	29/07/2022	online	GIG	English	1	67	International networks/associations
114	Social Media	Blog about 1st CoAct hangout 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:695881030804	29/07/2022	online	GIG	English	1	130	International networks/associations
115	Social Media	Open publication - Gilberto, English	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:695585347098	21/07/2022	online	GIG	English	1	128	International networks/associations
116	Social Media	CoAct hangout 3 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6945336256302	22/06/2022	online	GIG	English	1	98	International networks/associations
117	Social Media	CoAct hangout 3 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6942833063436	15/06/2022	online	GIG	English	1	181	International networks/associations
118	Social Media	CoAct hangout 3 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6932992588406	19/05/2022	online	GIG	English	1	184	International networks/associations
119	Social Media	CoAct hangout 2 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6928586273	21/06/2022	online	GIG	English	1	30	International networks/associations
120	Social Media	CoAct hangout 2 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6928586273	18/05/2022	online	GIG	English	1	53	International networks/associations
121	Social Media	CoAct hangout 2 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6920324615838	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	57	International networks/associations
122	Social Media	Join the public consultation on the 6 Principles of pe	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6920324615838	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	72	International networks/associations
123	Social Media	Blog about 1st CoAct hangout 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6924920542346	06/05/2022	online	GIG	English	1	72	International networks/associations
124	Social Media	CoAct hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6924920542346	27/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	53	International networks/associations
125	Social Media	CoAct hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6922861644746	21/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	19	International networks/associations
126	Social Media	ECSA Conference	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6922474167455	20/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	33	International networks/associations
127	Social Media	CoAct hangouts 2022 schedule	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6920324615838	14/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	36	International networks/associations
128	Social Media	CoAct hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6917745290523	07/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	54	International networks/associations
129	Social Media	CoAct hangout 1 - announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6917485342323	06/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	69	International networks/associations
130	Social Media	call for publications*	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6917091010493	05/04/2022	online	GIG	English	1	29	International networks/associations
131	Social Media	Global Perspectives Launch Event	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1600794316301107201?s=20&t=08/12/2022	08/12/2022	online	GIG	English	1	35	International networks/associations
132	Social Media	Discourse on Decolonizing the Education System in S	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1598225644315414528?s=20&t=07/11/2022	07/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	79	International networks/associations
133	Social Media	CoAct exhibition in Vienna	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15895892388231495689?s=20&t=07/11/2022	07/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	69	International networks/associations
134	Social Media	The recap of our 5th and final Global Perspectives	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1588078787892352609?s=20&t=03/11/2022	03/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	150	International networks/associations
135	Social Media	ownership of science by gilbertoviera - Global Persp	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15877776344309761?s=20&t=03/11/2022	03/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	150	International networks/associations
136	Social Media	CoAct playlist on Youtube	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/158777294453678081?s=20&t=02/11/2022	02/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	152	International networks/associations
137	Social Media	Global Perspectives Blog Post series	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1584811481951740182?s=20&t=25/10/2022	25/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	32	International networks/associations
138	Social Media	CoAct Final Event panel on Opportunities and hurdle	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1584562361838477314?s=20&t=24/10/2022	24/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	59	International networks/associations
139	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1582988491419701251?s=20&t=20/10/2022	20/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	289	International networks/associations
140	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/158266857509765411?s=20&t=19/10/2022	19/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	66	International networks/associations
141	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15822644717198540807?s=20&t=18/10/2022	18/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	122	International networks/associations
142	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1581963994037821441?s=20&t=17/10/2022	17/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	53	International networks/associations
143	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/158063524196487171?s=20&t=14/10/2022	14/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	58	International networks/associations
144	Social Media	The Whitepaper on Co-Evaluation of Citizen Social S	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1577642294240595973?s=20&t=05/10/2022	05/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	42	International networks/associations
145	Social Media	Last CoAct hangout 2022	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1572206244286369792?s=20&t=20/09/2022	20/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	68	International networks/associations
146	Social Media	CoAct hangout	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/157003639646154753?s=20&t=14/09/2022	14/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	62	International networks/associations
147	Social Media	Result of the gender open calls	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/1569959154789355618?s=20&t=14/09/2022	14/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	70	International networks/associations
148	Social Media	CoAct hangout - new date	https://twitter.com/weareGIG/status/15686016925024952347?s=20&t=05/09/2022	05/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	50	International networks/associations
149	Social Media	Global Perspectives Launch Event	https://www.instagram.com/p/CmHbVwKtJb/	14/12/2022	online	GIG	English	1	57	International networks/associations
150	Social Media	Democratization of Knowledge - Global Perspectives	https://www.instagram.com/p/CmKkMkAqNsz/	14/12/2022	online	GIG	English	1	37	International networks/associations
151	Social Media	The recap of her 5th and final Global Perspectives h	https://www.instagram.com/p/CkKfPeDThY/	03/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	70	International networks/associations
152	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://www.instagram.com/p/Cj7Zan_eNRXs/	10/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	58	International networks/associations
153	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://www.instagram.com/p/Cj4t07bNuij/	19/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	52	International networks/associations
154	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://www.instagram.com/p/Cj2RcUFT-I/	18/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	46	International networks/associations
155	Social Media	The Whitepaper on Co-Evaluation of Citizen Social S	https://www.instagram.com/p/CjVWYxkLef/	05/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	54	International networks/associations
156	Social Media	CoAct hangout	https://www.instagram.com/p/CjUwK610ZAJ/	20/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	62	International networks/associations
157	Social Media	CoAct hangout	https://www.instagram.com/p/CjFw6tRdQj/	14/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	54	International networks/associations
158	Social Media	Result of the gender open calls	https://www.instagram.com/p/CjEsRf0NjQj/	14/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	66	International networks/associations
159	Social Media	CoAct hangout - new date	https://www.instagram.com/p/CjISuWwqWjE/	05/09/2022	online	GIG	English	1	95	International networks/associations
160	Social Media	Democratization of Knowledge - Global Perspectives	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/photos/a.1589008298031005/33	14/12/2022	online	GIG	English	1	38	International networks/associations
161	Social Media	Global Perspectives Launch Event	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/photos/a.1589008298031005/33	08/12/2022	online	GIG	English	1	46	International networks/associations
162	Social Media	The recap of her 5th and final Global Perspectives h	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/photos/a.1589008298031005/33	03/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	112	International networks/associations
163	Social Media	CoAct co-publication: Global perspectives	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0WxSGBVnNlQvR	07/11/2022	online	GIG	English	1	105	International networks/associations
164	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0244ur0412X8LlKQz	26/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	25	International networks/associations
165	Social Media	CoAct final event - panel on Opportunities and hurdle	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0VtshJk74KqoAto	22/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	25	International networks/associations
166	Social Media	CoAct final event - panel on Opportunities and hurdle	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0244ur0412X8LlKQz	21/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	26	International networks/associations
167	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0244ur0412X8LlKQz	20/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	33	International networks/associations
168	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0244ur0412X8LlKQz	19/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	27	International networks/associations
169	Social Media	CoAct final event	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0244ur0412X8LlKQz	18/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	57	International networks/associations
170	Social Media	Newsletter: GIG news no 22 ft CoAct	https://www.facebook.com/wearegig/posts/pfbid0244ur0412X8LlKQz	17/10/2022	online	GIG	English	1	40	International networks/associations

Partner	DOI	Type of publication	Repository Link	Link to the publication	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proceedings/Books series/book (for book chapter)	Number, date or frequency of the Journal/Process entry/book	Relevant Pages	ISBN	Publisher	Place of Publication	Year of Publication	Is this publication available in Open-Access, or will it be made available?	Is at least one co-researcher a co-author?	Is the publication related with CoAct methodological framework?	Peer reviewed?	Estimated Reach	Target Group
ZSI Univie	Pos(ACSC)2020017	Conference paper	https://pos.sissa.it/393	https://doi.org/10.22323.3	"Hard to reach" or "easy to ignore": Strategies and reflections on including co-researchers	Wöhner V, Kerschhofer-Pühnik M, Kießlinger B, Mayer K, Schurz S, Truckenbroth S et al.	Proceedings of Science (Pos)	Apr. 12	--	--	Proceedings of Science (Pos)	Vienna	2020	Y	n	n	Y	150	EU and worldwide
UNIVE	https://doi.org/10.3329/feministaction.v5i1.68	article	--	https://www.budrich-journal.de	Einverständniserklärungen für eine feministische Forschungspraxis. Überlegungen zur prozesshaften Gestaltung und gesellschaftlichen Einbettung von Einwilligung	Veronica Wöhner, Teresa Winerstaller, Mariam Malik	Femina Politica	--	--	--	--	--	2021	Y	n	Y	Y	1200	EU and worldwide
UB	10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_11	Chapter in a book	https://link.springer.com/chap	https://link.springer.com/chap	Participation and Co-creation in Citizen Science	Eric Senabre Hidalgo, Josep Perelló, Frank Becker, Isabelle Bonnoire, Marine Legris, Anna Cigarini	The Science of Citizen Science	--	--	--	--	--	2021	Y	n	n	Y	17000	EU and worldwide
UB	10.1016/j.jstotenv.2021.147750	Research paper	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1548768321001090	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1548768321001090	Large-scale citizen science provides high-resolution nitrogen dioxide values and health impact while enhancing community knowledge and collective action	Josep Perelló, Anna Cigarini, Julian Vicens, Isabelle Bonnoire, David Foglia-Rueda, Markk. Neuenhuijzen, Marta Cirach, Carolyn Daher, Jaume Arza, V. Verheul, D. Friedel, S. K. P. Wong, Stefanie Schurz, Barbara Kießlinger, Teresa Schäfer	Science of the Total Environment	--	--	488697	Elsevier BV	--	2021	Y	n	Y	4000	EU and worldwide	
UB	10.1016/j.jstotenv.2021.101090	Research paper	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1548768321001090	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1548768321001090	Public libraries embrace citizen science: Strengths and challenges	Bonnoire, Julian Vicens, Josep Perelló, Aracibia, F. Verheul, D. Friedel, S. K. P. Wong, Stefanie Schurz, Barbara Kießlinger, Teresa Schäfer	Library & Information Science Research	--	--	--	Pergamon Press Ltd.	--	2021	Y	n	n	Y	150	EU and worldwide
UNSAM	https://doi.org/10.3334/cstb.400	Research paper	--	https://theoxandriactructe.org	Building Participatory Knowledge Infrastructure Against the GMO Agrusiness Regime: The Case of Los Campesinos Santiagos	Arza, V. Verheul, D. Friedel, S. K. P. Wong, Stefanie Schurz, Barbara Kießlinger, Teresa Schäfer	Citizen Science: Theory and Practice	In press	--	--	--	--	2022	Y	n	n	Y	133	EU and worldwide
ZSI	--	Chapter in a book	--	https://www.cambridge.org/core	Transformation messen und verstehen: partizipative Evaluationsansätze für Citizen Science	Mayer, Katja und Schurz, Stefanie und Kießlinger, Barbara	Zukunft gestalten mit Sozialen Innovationen	--	207-223	9783593451268	Campus Verlag	--	2022	Y	n	Y	Y	50	EU and worldwide
ZSI	10.22163/fresal.2022.566	Editorial	https://repository.fresal.org	https://repository.fresal.org	Participatory Evaluation and Impact Assessment in Citizen Science	Mayer, Katja und Schurz, Stefanie und Kießlinger, Barbara und Schäfer, Teresa	fresal Journal for Research and Technology	--	05-Sep	--	Fresal	--	2022	Y	n	Y	n	150	EU and worldwide
ZSI	Pos(ACSC)2021	Conference paper	--	--	Adapting public funding schemes for participatory research: Managing expectations, overcoming structural constraints	Marschall, Lisa, Kießlinger, Barbara, Schurz, Stefanie, Schäfer, Teresa	Proceedings of Science (Pos)	--	--	--	--	--	2022	Y	n	Y	Y	20	EU and worldwide
UNIVE	https://doi.org/10.17645/ia.v4i02.3193	Research paper	--	https://www.ceasatpress.eu	"They Really Only Look for the Best": How Young People Frame Problems in School-to-Work Transition	Veronica Wöhner, Shejia Danz, Mariam Malik	Social Inclusion	Vol. 10 Nr. 2	335-346	--	coeditato	--	2022	Y	n	Y	Y	650	EU and worldwide
ZSI	10.22163/fresal.2022.567	Research paper	https://repository.fresal.org	https://repository.fresal.org	Participatory evaluation practices in citizen social science: Insights from three case studies	Mayer, K., & Schurz, T. (2021).	fresal Journal for Research and Technology	--	--	--	--	--	2022	Y	n	Y	Y	50	EU and worldwide
ZSI, UB	doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_7	Chapter in a book	https://link.springer.org	https://link.springer.org	Citizen Social Science: New and Established Approaches to Participation in Social Research	Mayer, K., & Schurz, T. (2021).	Springer, Cham	--	--	978-3-030-58278-4	Springer, Cham	--	2021	Y	n	Y	Y	16000	EU and worldwide
ZSI	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4	Chapter in a book	https://link.springer.com/book	https://link.springer.com/book	Evaluation in Citizen Science: The Art of Tracing a Moving Target	Schaefer, T., Kießlinger, B., Brandt, M., van den Bogaert, V.	Springer, Cham	--	--	978-3-030-58278-4	Springer, Cham	--	2021	Y	n	Y	Y	428000	EU and worldwide

1053

Reach Phase 2

466500

Reach Phase 1

Summary Target Groups
EU and worldwide researchers
467553

Partner	Event title	Type of event	Date	Type of audience	Geographic level of the event	Number of participants (average)	What was the topic/purpose of this event?	Link to programme	What was your role?	Other coAct partners collaborating? Who?	Link to ppt/material presented? (url)	Notes
UNWIE	Exhibition - Participatory research with young people from to 18 ⁺ Vienna/Austria	Exhibition	09/11/2022	Civil society	EU	90	Connecting with nurses, makers, and innovators who shared their work experiences and ideas on how to navigate the Corona-Crisis and support local communities with open technologies. DOTs brings together people interested in impact driven innovation, emancipatory technology, open source, and maker culture. We hosted workshops, sessions, meetups, panels as well as sharing music, movement and making sure we stay connected. CoAct was presented in the Open Science meetup with other projects in Cameroon, Nigeria, Brazil.	https://www.digitalinnovationathene.org/dot-s/0405-2022/	Organiser and host	No	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGUP	
GIG	DOTS Conference	Organisation of a Conference	10/11/2020	Civil society	International	70	Discussing the impact of digital youth work, giving best practice examples and guidelines/support for youth workers	https://coactproject.eu/news/coact-webinar-co-creating-evaluation-in-citizen-science/	Organisers			
ZSI	Webinar: Co-shaping evaluation in citizen science?	Organisation of a Conference	24/01/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	International	40	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=56r-2021	Organisers	GIG supporting with promotion		
Univie	Taller: Digital youth work, Challenges, tools and impact.	Organisation of a Conference	05/05/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	International	20	This time we discussed the framing of science by learning how scientifically rigor research is done outside academia. We want to take a global perspective, learning from participatory research initiatives in different contexts	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=56r-2021	Workshop organiser			
UNSAM	Foro: Horizontes de la coproducción de conocimiento científico. At "Jornadas de Fundamentos y Aplicaciones de la Interdisciplina".	Organisation of a Conference	19/05/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	National	20	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=56r-2021	Workshop organiser			
GIG	Rethinking Science: learning from research rooted within civil society	Organisation of a Conference	22/06/2021	Civil society	International	14	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/coact-webinar-june-22nd-2021/	Organiser and facilitator			
GIG	Shaping a critical and open approach to Gender Equality in the Citizen Social Science	Organisation of a Conference	23/11/2021	Civil society	International	11	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser and facilitator			
GIG	DOTS Conference	Organisation of a Conference	30/11/2021	Civil society	International	35	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser and host	No		
UNWIE	Train-the-Trainers: Actionbound zum Thema Ausbildung und Beruf	Organisation of a Conference	14/12/2021	Civil society	National	5	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
GIG	Final Event Week	Organisation of a Conference	18/10/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	EU & International	240	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
GIG	CoAct FFP Perspectives Launch	Organisation of a Conference	14/12/2022	Civil society	EU & International	20	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
UB	CoAct FFP Perspectives Launch	Organisation of a Conference	14/12/2022	Civil society	EU & International	20	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
GIG	CoAct FFP Perspectives Launch	Organisation of a Conference	14/12/2022	Civil society	EU & International	20	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
UB	CoAct FFP Perspectives Launch	Organisation of a Conference	14/12/2022	Civil society	EU & International	20	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
UNSAM/FARN	Citizen Social Science for Environmental Justice in Riechuelo	Organisation of a Workshop	29/10/2020	EU and worldwide researchers	EU & International	30	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
UB	Citizen Social Science and Complex Systems Science / Coping social issues with active citizen participation	Organisation of a Workshop	09/12/2020	Civil society	International	40	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
GIG	1st Community hangout	Organisation of a Workshop	20/04/2021	Civil society	International	19	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
ZSI	Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Science	Organisation of a Workshop	12/05/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	International	25	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
UNSAM	Taller de reconocimiento de bibliotecas de la ciencia Red CONAUIP	Organisation of a Workshop	26/05/2021	Civil society	Local	9	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
UNWIE	„Das muss noch unterschrieben werden...“ Einverständniserklärungen in der empirischen Sozialforschung aus rechtlicher und ethischer Perspektive	Organisation of a Workshop	01/09/2021	Civil society	International	15	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser and facilitator			
GIG	Citizen Science Summer School Workshop Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times	Organisation of a Workshop	15/09/2021	Civil society	International	30	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
ZSI	"Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Science", Workshop at the 1st Global Transdisciplinarity Conference	Organisation of a Workshop	27/09/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	International	24	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
GIG	Gender-equality hangout	Organisation of a Workshop	21/10/2021	Civil society	International	4	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser and facilitator			
GIG	Collaboration dynamics in cross-disciplinary teams.	Organisation of a Workshop	18/11/2021	Civil society	International	10	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
UNSAM	Sesión temática sobre Co-producción de conocimiento en contextos de problemáticas socio-ambientales Congreso CACIAR (ciencia abierta y ciudadana)	Organisation of a Workshop	03/12/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	International	30	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
FHP	Workshop I: Research Question and Design	Organisation of a Workshop	17/12/2021	Civil society	Local	5	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
FHP	Workshop II: Research Question and Literature Review	Organisation of a Workshop	25/01/2022	Civil society	Local	7	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			
GIG	Locally driven protocols and local traditions in the Open Citizen Social Sciences	Organisation of a Workshop	21/04/2022	Civil society	EU & International	6	CoAct FFP organised a workshop on knowledge-co-production an CoAct was presented	https://coactproject.eu/news/webinar-nov-23rd-2021/	Organiser			

GIG	The Ownership of Science	Environmental awareness workshop at educational institution	Organisation of a Workshop	19/05/2022	Civil society	EU & International	unpack the question of what role Citizen Social Science can or should play in bringing Science back to its 'original owners'. To disseminate the R&I action. To raise environmental awareness and spread the concept of Citizen Social Science. To disseminate the use of CCS as a tool for environmental education.	Organiser	https://coactproject.eu/news/diversifying-the-ownership-of-science-lessons-from-our-3rd-community-hangout/	No	3 co-researcher
UNSAM	Environmental awareness workshop at educational institution	Organisation of a Workshop	20/05/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	National	Barcelona	30 Care and R&I Action on Environmental Justice	Co-organisers	https://comunitat.catedrom.barcelona/assemblees/comunitat/11651/meetings/23887/assemblee-slug-comunitat&component_id=1651&locale=en	No	3 co-researcher
UB	Jornades CoActuem. Salut mental i justícia mediambiental	Organisation of a Workshop	31/05/2022	Civil society	Barcelona	30 Care and R&I Action on Environmental Justice	Decolonizing our educational/institutional influences - Towards open science funding and mental decolonization • CoAct (coactproject.eu)	Organiser	https://coactproject.eu/news/overcoming-false-representations-nurturing-a-shared-understanding-of-concepts-and-opening-up-knowledge-in-cross-disciplinary-research/	FSMC, UNSAM	3 co-researcher
GIG	Decolonizing our educational/institutional influences - Towards open science funding and mental decolonization	Organisation of a Workshop	23/06/2022	Civil society	EU & International	German speaking	6 how to decolonize our educational/institutional influences	Organiser	https://coactproject.eu/news/overcoming-false-representations-nurturing-a-shared-understanding-of-concepts-and-opening-up-knowledge-in-cross-disciplinary-research/	Workshop-organizer and facilitator	
ZSI	Decolonizing our educational/institutional influences - Towards open science funding and mental decolonization	Organisation of a Workshop	26/06/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	EU & International	German speaking	6 how to decolonize our educational/institutional influences	Organiser	https://coactproject.eu/news/overcoming-false-representations-nurturing-a-shared-understanding-of-concepts-and-opening-up-knowledge-in-cross-disciplinary-research/	Workshop-organizer and facilitator	
GIG	Overcoming False Representation - Nurturing a shared understanding of concepts and opening up knowledge in cross-disciplinary research	Organisation of a Workshop	15/09/2022	Civil society	EU & International	Local	11 and community stakeholders.	Organiser	https://coactproject.eu/news/overcoming-false-representations-nurturing-a-shared-understanding-of-concepts-and-opening-up-knowledge-in-cross-disciplinary-research/	Organiser	
UNSAM/FARN	Zoom presentation of the platform for community actors	Organisation of a Workshop	15/09/2022	Civil society	Local	Local	11 and community stakeholders.	Co-organisers and facilitators	https://coactproject.eu/news/overcoming-false-representations-nurturing-a-shared-understanding-of-concepts-and-opening-up-knowledge-in-cross-disciplinary-research/	No	
GIG	Ethical Barcodes Setting in CCS communities. Satellite at the Conference on Complex Systems 2022: "AMETHYST: GAME THEORY in complex Systems"	Organisation of a Workshop	22/09/2022	Civil society	EU & International	EU & International	6 how to decolonize our educational/institutional influences	Organiser	https://coactproject.eu/news/overcoming-false-representations-nurturing-a-shared-understanding-of-concepts-and-opening-up-knowledge-in-cross-disciplinary-research/	Organiser	
UB	AMETHYST: GAME THEORY in complex Systems"	Organisation of a Workshop	22/10/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	International	International	70 Science discipline	Co-Organizer	https://amethystatellite.weebly.com/program.html	Organiser	
UNVIE	#2 Youth Employment.	Organisation of a Workshop	08/11/2022	EU policy makers	Local	Local	40 Presentation of the project results	Organiser		Organiser	
UNVIE	Panediscussion "Transforming social policy through participatory research? Challenges, objectives and achievements"	Organisation of a Workshop	10/11/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	Local	Local	19 Discussing the potential of participatory research approaches to approve them. To disseminate these results to a wide audience, especially policy makers.	Organiser		Organiser	
UB	Assemblea Comunitat Salut Mental de CoActuem per la Salut Mental	Organisation of a Workshop	18/11/2022	EU policy makers	Catalonia	Catalonia	80 policy makers.	Co-organizer	https://www.cs-sfsg-conference-berlin/en/programme/evening-event.html	FSMC	Active participa
UB	Citizen Science is Social!	Other	15/10/2020	EU policy makers	EU	EU	500 Disseminate the concept of Citizen Social Science	Organizer	https://twitter.com/fund_cmsf/status/1469317006713045000?s=20	UNSAM, FARN, UNVIE	
UNSAM	Conversatorio de ciencia ciudadana.Red Uagais	Other	17/11/2021	EU policy makers	National	National	63 about other CC projects in Argentina. The main goal is to offer academic researchers a common space and a shared time to reflect, discuss, learn, and receive practical guidelines to explore social dimensions such as a wide set of Citizen Science practices related to social issues, about involving groups and persons in a vulnerable situation acting as co-researchers.	Co-organiser	https://coactproject.eu/citizen-social-science-school-social-dimensions-in-citizen-science/	No	
UB	Citizen Social Science Summer School	Training	23/09/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	International	International	40	Organizer and facilitator	https://coactproject.eu/citizen-social-science-school-social-dimensions-in-citizen-science/	Yes: ZSI, UNVIE, FHP, UNSAM, GIG.	

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ACTIONS' SUMMARY	Phase1	Phase2
Organisation of a Conference	2	2
Organisation of a Workshop	3	24
Other	1	1
Training	0	1
Exhibition	0	1

Summary Target Groups	0
Vulnerable citizens	665
Civil society	0
Local administrations	77
EU and worldwide researchers	683
International networks/associations	
EU policy makers	

UB	Conference on Complex Systems 2022	Participation to a Conference	22/10/2022	70	International	EU and worldwide researchers	10-researche	https://www.cc2022.org/index.php/programme/programme-at-a-glance https://livingknowledge.org/19	N	onsite, Palma d
UB	9th Living Knowledge Conference	Participation to a Conference	01/07/2022	20	Chadonia	EU and worldwide researchers	1 to-researche	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	Y	onsite, Götting
UNSAM	Guillermo Adis member of CoAct facilitates a public policy session at Gathering of Open Science Hardware (GOSH) in Panamá	Participation to a Conference	27/10/2022	80	International	EU and worldwide researchers	1 to-researche	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	Y	onsite
UB	ECSA CONFERENCE // 2022	Participation to a Conference	08/10/2022	100	International	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	onsite, Berlin, C
UB	ECSA CONFERENCE // 2022	Participation to a Conference	08/10/2022	35	International	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	onsite, Berlin, C
UB	European Investing Funds in People (2021-2027) Opportunities for the Social Sector of Catalonia	Participation to a Workshop	25/11/2020	150	Local	EU policy makers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	14/09/2021	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	12/05/2021	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	14/07/2021	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	05/09/2021	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	05/09/2021	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	13/10/2021	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Acostem la clínica als nostres barris i municipis	Participation to a Workshop	25/11/2021	50	Local	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	08/12/2021	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Per ciència ciutadana a la Universitat de Barcelona	Participation to a Workshop	10/12/2021	50	Local	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	face to face
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	12/01/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Swifts sisters projects on Citizen Science	Participation to a Workshop	09/03/2022	30	International	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Invited talk at 7th Annual Workshop on Complex Sociotechnical Systems	Participation to a Workshop	31/03/2022	80	National	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	11/05/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Jornades CoActum, Salut mental i justícia mediambiental	Participation to a Workshop	31/05/2022	30	Barcelona	Civil society		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	Y	onsite, Barcelona
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	08/06/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	Y	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	13/07/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	Y	online
UNSAM	Presentation at II Workshop of the Citizen Science Brazilian Network	Participation to a Workshop	09/08/2022	31	Regional	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	14/09/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Invited talk to Jornades Hacia una nueva cultura científica (Universitat Politècnica de València)	Participation to a Workshop	27/09/2022	60	National	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	onsite, València
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	12/10/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Networking Brunch UC3M: Guest speaker, Citizen Science	Participation to a Workshop	14/10/2022	50	Local	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	onsite, Madrid,
UNIVE	Meeting of the Tyrollian steering group about young people not in education, training or employment	Participation to a Workshop	18/10/2022	20	Local	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UNIVE	Meeting of the advisory board of the Education and Training up to 18 programme	Participation to a Workshop	25/10/2022	30	Local	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	09/11/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Presentation at the Workshop "CitMeasure, Barcelona Training"	Participation to a Workshop	17/11/2022	50	International	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Assemblea Comunitat Salut Mental de CoActum per la Salut Mental	Participation to a Workshop	18/11/2022	1	Catalonia	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	onsite, Barcelona
UB	Presentation at the Workshop "Data Science in/for Barcelona"	Participation to a Workshop	30/11/2022	50	Local	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	onsite, Barcelona
UNIVE	Kontraktgruppenauffbau Ausbildung bis 18 & Übergang Schule Beruf Niederösterreich	Participation to a Workshop	07/12/2022	30	Local	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	onsite
ZSI	Joint Swifts Citizen Science Working Group	Participation to a Workshop	14/12/2022	20	EU, international	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
UB	Festival de Innovación Abierta Frena la Curva	Participation to other Event	02/05/2020	18,000	International (Sp)	Civil society		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	More informat
UNSAM	UNESCO Regional Consultation on Open Science for Latin America and the Caribbean	Participation to other Event	23/09/2020	70	International (La)	National institutions		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	Montevideo on
UNSAM	UNDP	Participation to other Event	29/10/2020	110	International (Ar)	National institutions		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	online
ZSI	WebObserve CoP Presentation: Participatory Evaluation Approaches in CS	Participation to other Event	04/03/2021	20	International	EU and worldwide researchers		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435355	N	-

UB	Jornades Culturals Facultat de Psicologia de la Universitat de Barcelona	Participation to other Event	09/05/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	Catalonia	15	Presentation by Isabelle Bonhoure (UB) and Ana Vázquez / Vicenç Mateo (CoAct for Mental Health Co-Researches) to disseminate the R&I section. To inform and promote its use among neighbors and community stakeholders.	Y	https://www.ub.edu/portal/web/psicologia/detail/4-de-maig-activitats-per-les-jornades-culturals-psicologia	2 co-researche onsite, Barcelor
UNSAM/FARN	Presentation at the Buenos Aires Museums Night	Participation to other Event	22/10/2022	Civil society	Local	20	During the event Valeria Arca commented on the potential of citizen social science and shared the experience of CoAct's RY Action in Buenos Aires. The report will be presented as a result of the work done by the National Committee of Citizen Science in which Valeria Arca, director CoAct's R&A Action in Buenos Aires, has been taking part.	N	https://www.diba.cat/document/1166883825509	on site
UNSAM	Official Launch event: Presentation of the National Citizen Science Programme at the National Ministry	Participation to other Event	31/10/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	National	100		N		on site
UNSAM	Official Launch event: Presentation of the Open Science Committee's Final Report at the National Ministry	Participation to other Event	10/11/2022	EU and worldwide researchers	National	20		N	unpublished yet	on site
UB	Presentation at "Treball i salut mental: 20 anys trencant estigmes"	Participation to other Event	24/11/2022	EU policy makers	Local	120	Presentation by Isabelle Bonhoure: CoAct for Mental Health	n	https://www.ub.edu/ub/web/1166883825509	on site, Sant Bo
UB	Lifelong Professional Training for researchers: "Research Social Impact"	Training	17/02/2021	EU and worldwide researchers	Local	205	Presentation of CoAct to insist on the social dimension in research projects.	N	https://www.ub.edu/ub/web/1166883825509	Barcelona onlin

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Reach Phase 2

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Actions' Summary	Phase1	Phase2
Other	2	2
Participation to a Conference	18	39
Participation to a Workshop	1	30
Participation to other Event	4	5
Training	1	0

Material Distribution

Partner	Type of material distributed	Event/occasion in which you distributed the material	How many material did you distribute?	Target audience?	Reach Approx.	Date	Notes
UNIVIE	Flyer	Introduction Day in 'AusbildungFit' institution	10	Civil society	20	2021	Printed material handed out to young people/co-researchers
UB	Research Notebook	Kick-off of co-creation sessions with Co-Researchers	30	EU and worldwide researchers	60	2021	Printed material sent to co-researchers
GIG	Flyer	Introducing: What is CoAct?	Online	Civil society	100	2021	
GIG	Flyers (English, German, Spanish, Whitepaper	Introducing: What is CoAct?	300	Civil society	600	2021	
ZSI	Whitepaper	ECSA Conference 2022	20	EU and worldwide researchers	40	2022	
ZSI	fteval special issue	ECSA Conference 2022	10	EU and worldwide researchers	20	2022	
UNIVIE	Report	Presentation of results as part of the exhibition on the research findings of R&I Action #2 Youth Employment.	50	EU policy makers	100	2022	Printed material - https://zenodo.org/record/7390893#.Y6Q-K-ZOE5
UNIVIE	Report	Presentation of results as part of the exhibition on the research findings of R&I Action #2 Youth Employment.	Online	EU policy makers	100		Same as the printed report available online at https://coactproject.univie.ac.at/wien-par/fab-das-forschungsspiel-zu-ausbildung-und-beruf/
			780				
			Reach phase 1	Reach Phase 2	260		

Summary Target Groups	Count
Vulnerable citizens	0
Civil society	720
Local administrations	0
EU and worldwide researchers	120
International networks/associations	0
EU policy makers	200